

University of Cologne
Institute for Media Culture and Theatre

Bachelor Thesis

Dr. phil. habil. Mathias Mertens

Summer Semester 2022

**What are the effects of Social Media and Screen
Time on Mental Health? A discussion of
relevant literature**

Aleksandar Dragomirov

BA – Verbund: Medienkulturwissenschaft und Medienmanagement und –
ökonomie

E-Mail:

50931 Köln

Matrikelnummer:

Table of Contents

List of Figures	4
List of Tables.....	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Basic Terminology and Conceptual Foundations	7
2.1. Social Media	8
2.2. Screen Time.....	9
2.3. Mental Health	10
2.4. Social Media and Mental Health	11
2.5. Screen Time and Mental Health.....	12
3. Theoretical Foundations and Hypothesis.....	12
3.1. Theoretical Foundations	13
3.1.1. Current Research on Social Media and Mental Health	13
3.1.2. Current Research on Screen Time and Mental Health.....	15
3.1.3. Screen Time and Brain Development.....	16
3.2. Hypothesis.....	17
4. Method and Data	18
4.1. Search strategy.....	19
4.2. Study selection	20
5. Results	21
5.1. Study Methodologies	21
5.2. Summary of the results	21
5.3. Key Themes	22
5.3.1. Potential benefits	22
5.3.2. Screen time and mental health.....	25
5.3.3. Adverse effects.....	27
5.3.4. Mediators	33
6. Discussions	38
6.1. Summary of the findings	39
6.2. Interpretations	39
6.2.1. Potential benefits	40
6.2.2. Screen time and mental health.....	40
6.2.3. Adverse effects.....	41
6.2.4. Mediators	41
6.3. Implications.....	42

6.4. Limitations	43
6.5. Recommendations	43
7. Conclusion	44
8. References.....	46
Appendix	56

List of Figures

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram

List of Tables

Table 1: Keyword combination, database, and number of results

Keyword	Database	Number of results
social media[Title]	PubMed	4,766
screen time[Title]	PubMed	618
mental health[Title]	PubMed	23,922
(social media[Title]) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	136
(screen time[Title]) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	16
((social media[Title]) OR (screen time[Title])) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	150

Table 2: Methodology of the included articles

Method	Number of studies
Cross-Sectional	14
Review	12
Longitudinal	7
Quantitative	4
Qualitative	3
Specification Curve Analysis	1

Randomized Controlled Trial	1
Meta-Analysis	1

Table 4: Overview of the Key Themes

	Social Media Benefits	Social Media Adverse Effects				Screen Time and Mental Health
		Depression	Anxiety	Social Effects	Self-Harm	
Number of Studies	11	13	4	5	6	9

1. Introduction

The popularity and usage of social media are growing exponentially during the past years. Over 3.6 billion individuals worldwide used social media in 2020 and it is suggested that this number could grow to 4.41 billion by 2025 (Statista 2022). At the same time, screen time of teenagers in the United States increased twice during the timespan of 10 years (between 2006 and 2016) (Twenge, Martin, and Spitzberg 2018) and as of 2021 more than two-thirds of all American adults are actively using the most popular platform Facebook (Gramlich 2021). All those events coincide with a global mental health epidemic. Mental health problems are on the rise all around the globe. More disturbing is the fact that around 20% of the world's children and adolescents suffer from some kind of mental illness, while suicide is the second largest cause of mortality among those aged between 15 and 29 (WHO 2022). All those occurrences raise the question of whether or not social media or screen time are connected to mental health in any way. Social media research has changed dramatically in recent years, with the potential link between social media and mental health becoming a controversial and often researched topic. Different studies explore different aspects of both social media and screen time, different social media platforms and also different mental health outcomes (Schønning et al. 2020), while some concentrate on the catalyst role of the recent Covid-19 pandemic on social media and mental health (Valdez et al. 2020).

This study will try to best summarize the existing literature around social media, screen time and their connection to mental health and will try to properly and in detail answer the question “What are the effects of social media and screen time on mental health?”. First, this paper will explore the conceptual foundations of social media, screen time and mental health, and will summarize the different definitions. After that, the theoretical foundations will be established and a hypothesis will be constructed. The next chapter will introduce the choice of method, the procedure, and the final data sample. After that, the results will be systematically presented and later summarized, analysed, and interpreted. Finally, potential research gaps will be identified and named and this review will give recommendations for future research.

2. Basic Terminology and Conceptual Foundations

The goal of this chapter is to present a terminological framework and introduce the reader to the concepts that are later going to be discussed in this paper. The understanding of these key concepts is crucial in investigating the research question and would set the

foundations for presenting the answers and the findings. The following literature aims to explain terms such as *social media*, *screen time* and *mental health*, but also illustrate their nuances and name different influencers and catalysts in the relationships between social media and mental health and screen time and mental health. The conceptual foundation and the terminology will allow the development of the rationale and the structure of the paper.

2.1. Social Media

The social media phenomenon refers to different platforms, such as content sharing sites, social networking sites, or even blogs, where users can create, share, or discuss internet content. Photos, videos, messages and personal information are just a few examples of the forms internet content could take (Kietzmann et al. 2011, p.242).

Recent research indicates that young people use social media in various ways and for different reasons. One of them is social enhancement. That is the improvement of social status using online engagements and actions. Forming the identity is another way the youth uses social media, maintains relationships, or simply for pure entertainment (Ifinedo 2016).

Similarly, according to Kietzmann, social media consists of seven fundamental conceptions. Identity, sharing, presence, relationships, conversations, reputation, and groups do not necessarily have to be included in every social media activity, and they are not exclusive of each other. Instead, they illustrate how different aspects of social media function (Kietzmann et al. 2011). Facebook is a perfect representative of an identity-based platform. People are required to enter their personal information in order to create a profile.

The identity functional block represents the extent to which users reveal their identities in a social media setting. This can include disclosing information such as name, age, gender, profession, location, and also information that portrays users in certain ways. (2011, p.243)

Other aspects around which social media is built are conversations and sharing. Users are messaging, blogging or tweeting with the goal of finding people with the same mindset. A lot of social media platforms are based on conversations, for example, Facebook and Twitter (Kietzmann et al. 2011).

In their definition of social network sites, Danah Boyd and Nicole Ellison present them as a “bounded system” where users can take part as they create a profile, make a list

of other users with whom they are connected and explore their connections within the system, as well as those made by others (2007, p. 2).

Another building block of social media is sharing. Sharing is the flow of content that is happening on social media. When users are sharing they are creating an opportunity for a conversation to start and the conversation could eventually turn into a relationship (2011). The term relationship from the perspective of social media is illustrated in the following segment:

The relationships block represents the extent to which users can be related to other users. By ‘relate,’ we mean that two or more users have some form of association that leads them to converse, share objects of sociality, meet up, or simply just list each other as a friend or fan (2011, p. 246).

According to Statista, the share of active social media users in Europe has increased from one-fifth of the population (20 %) in 2011 to almost half of the population (48%) in the European Union in 2019 (Statista 2020). That is one more argument about the increasing popularity of social media communication in the 21st century. (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019). At the same time, more than 70% of the public uses at least one of the social media platforms in the USA, with YouTube and Facebook being the two most popular. Instagram, Twitter, Pinterest, Snapchat and LinkedIn are also among the most used social media platforms by Americans (Pew Research Center 2018).

Since the delivery of the first E-mail in 1971, the evolution in communication technology has been immense. Between 2000 and 2006 social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter were launched. As a result of the digital media revolution, print media has seen a decline in popularity. Smartphones have greatly facilitated the growth of digital media and made the use of social media “almost inescapable” (Srivastava et al. 2019).

2.2. Screen Time

Recent years have seen a dramatic increase in screen time, particularly in the amount of time spent on computers or the Internet. Such news have the potential to be disturbing and point out the need for intervention and balance in the usage (Bucksch et al. 2014).

The concepts of social media and screen time are interlinked in many ways (Barthorpe et al. 2020). Screen time could be easily defined by time spent watching television or videos, playing video games, using a computer or using any electronic device that has a screen (Anderson, Economos, and Must 2008), as the time spent on screens or simply as the time spent using a screen (Paulich et al. 2021) (Smith et al. 2020).

One characteristic of screen time and one of the main reasons why screen time is considered a growing problem around the world is sedentary behaviour. Sedentary behaviour has the potential to negatively impact adults and adolescents and under some circumstances even children. (de Rezende et al. 2014) (Nigg et al. 2021).

A relatively new phenomenon, strongly connected to screen time and sedentary behaviour is binge-watching (Starosta and Izydorczyk 2020) (Raza et al. 2021). Binge-watching is defined as watching several episodes in a short amount of time (Pittman and Steiner 2021). That behaviour has become the focus of a recent study, investigating the relationship between screen time spent as binge-watching and psychological mental health (2021).

An important part of screen time research, particularly when connections between screen time and mental health are investigated, is physical activity (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018) (Nigg et al. 2021). A study from 2018 demonstrates that Icelandic adolescents with the lowest risk of mental health issues also reported fewer screen time hours combined with physical activity on a more regular basis (2018). Another longitudinal study set in Germany also investigated the role of physical activity in preventing mental health problems in adolescents, further demonstrating the importance of the topic (2021).

2.3. Mental Health

Worldwide, 10-20% of children and adolescents are suffering from some kind of mental health disorder. Considering that children and adolescents are one-third of the world's population, one can imagine the magnitude of that problem (Kieling et al. 2011, p.1515). In a perfect world, early intervention would prevent adolescent and child mental health problems from arising (2011, p.1519). The World Health Organization gives mental health the following definition:

Mental health is a state of well-being, in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to make a contribution to his or her community (2019).

Mental health itself can be influenced by the personal characteristics of an individual, social conditions and the environment. Depression, anxiety and psychosis are examples of the most common mental health disturbances. Mental health disorders affect a person's thoughts and emotions and therefore result in a variety of behavioural and relationship changes (2019). Other mental health problems include loneliness, suicidal thoughts, decreased empathy and social anxiety (Berryman, Ferguson, and Negy 2018).

However, there are a few problems with the WHO definition of mental health as it is built around positive feelings and positive functioning as the main factors. People in perfect mental health are free to feel a full palette of emotions that are not necessarily positive or pleasant because of the challenges of life itself. Therefore a more precise definition of mental health is needed. One that takes into account the dynamics of everyday life, human communication and emotional intelligence (Galderisi et al. 2015, p.231).

Mental health is a dynamic state of internal equilibrium which enables individuals to use their abilities in harmony with universal values of society. Basic cognitive and social skills; ability to recognize, express and modulate one's own emotions, as well as empathize with others (2015, p.232).

Other important parts of mental health include the ability to overcome everyday challenges while being an active member of society and a "harmonious relationship between body and mind" (2015, p.232).

2.4. Social Media and Mental Health

It is crucial for the relationship between social media and mental health to be better understood (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p. 3). The benefits and negative effects of social media on mental health are currently being debated and discussed (Berryman, Ferguson, and Negy 2018). Current studies are exploring the connections between social media and the sense of self, between social media and self-harm, and if social media addiction is affecting mental health in any way (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020). The role of parenthood in regulating social media time for children and adolescents (Fardouly et al. 2018) and the possibility of social media being used to promote mental health were also investigated (O'Reilly et al. 2019).

A cross-sectional study suggests that routine use of social media is associated with positive mental health effects while users who develop an emotional connection to their social media account tend to experience negative mental health consequences (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019).

Social media use is a relatively new phenomenon, and this contributes to the difficulties for researchers to find existing patterns and associations but also advocates for the need for new methods of examination. Some authors suggest that the conventional dose-effect approach in researching connections between social media and mental health may be insufficient and a new methodology, that takes into account different variables in

the social media use behaviour should be implemented (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019) (Barthorpe et al. 2020).

2.5. Screen Time and Mental Health

Mental health and screen time are inextricably linked. As of 2016, the average senior in high school spent more than twice as much time online compared to 2006. Furthermore, online time, texting time, and social media time are equal to six hours a day in 2016 (Twenge, Martin, and Spitzberg 2018). Such growing numbers of enhanced use and excessive screen time, together with findings of current studies, suggest a connection between screen time and self-harm in females (Barthorpe et al. 2020) and a connection between screen time and depression (Tang et al. 2021) pose a serious concern.

Smartphones are an ever-increasing phenomenon of the 21st century. As of 2019, more than 5 billion people own some kind of a mobile device, with half of that number being smartphones (Silver 2019). Recent studies suggest that the relationship between smartphone screen time and mental health problems is complicated and that the type of usage also plays a role in affecting mental health outcomes. For example, screen time used for socializing and screen time used for other non-social activities are completely different in terms of their relationship with mental health (Woo et al. 2021).

A lot of factors such as gender and age, different behaviour patterns, the activity level of an individual and the type of screen time all influence the relationship between screen time and mental health and should all be taken into account when researching this topic (de Rezende et al. 2014) (Nigg et al. 2021) (Twenge and Farley 2021, p. 208).

3. Theoretical Foundations and Hypothesis

The current review summarises and discusses relevant literature and findings on the connection between *social media*, *screen time*, and *mental health*. Such literature discussion contributes to the existing research by closely inspecting many sides of the social media phenomenon, exploring its connection with screen time and finally following social media and screen time's many interactions with mental health and the possible mental health outcomes. Furthermore, this paper allows future researchers to systematically analyse previous findings, evaluate their strengths and weaknesses, and find existing gaps in the literature. The research question "What are the effects of Social Media and Screen Time on Mental Health?" best summarises the purpose of the review.

3.1. Theoretical Foundations

Defining *social media* is a difficult problem in the twenty-first century because technology is rapidly advancing. One part of the technology evolution is the constant invention of social media platforms, that are often mutually replaceable. Another difficulty in sculpting a clear concept of social media is the Covid-19 pandemic that put users in an unusual situation where digital communication united different forms of social media with other communication technologies such as telephone and e-mail. There is a shift between the starting goal of social media serving as a communication channel and a social enhancement method and the recent usage of social media as content discovery and consumption strategy. Moreover, there seems to be no agreement on how *social media* addiction should be defined and also it is debatable if spending too much time on social media services is an addictive behavioural disorder (Haddad et al. 2021, p.7f).

3.1.1. Current Research on Social Media and Mental Health

Before researching the topic, several databases were used for systematic reviews that covered the subject to be identified. This approach would allow different frameworks to be compared and contrasting conclusions explored and understood. Therefore the quality and contribution of the current review would be maximised. Since the beginning of the century, the number of papers conducted on social media and mental health connections has increased significantly. Comparable rise is also seen in the different forms of social media (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020). Therefore, a systematic review from 2020 also focused on social media's effects on mental health. The research was conducted on various databases and covered a timeframe of almost 30 years. The final sample consisted of 16 studies, divided into groups depending on reported social media influence on mental health (positive, negative and neutral effects). Out of the sixteen studies included, five (31.25%) reported a positive influence of social media on mental health. Half of them reported diverse negative effects of social media on mental health. Finally, the rest three articles reported no significant association between social media and mental health. The systematic review presents mixed results, such as the potential benefits and adverse effects of social media on mental health. It acknowledges the need for more randomised control trials and longitudinal studies to explore the association between social media and mental health and to evaluate the variation in results between different age groups (2020, p.4ff).

Another systematic review, published in 2020, explored how social media influences anxiety, depression and psychological distress in adolescents. The review includes 13 studies, 12 of which cross-sectional and one longitudinal study, with a total sample of the studies 21, 231 participants. Most of the studies focused on general social media use and four chose to investigate the social platform Facebook in particular. The psychological condition that was most often investigated for connection to social media use was depression. The social media activities that were taken into account were excessive or addictive use of social media, frequency of the checking for messages and personal investment in the social media profile or image. Findings suggest a general connection between social media use and negative mental health outcomes, but the review also takes into account the different mediators (such as insomnia and sleep disturbances) in this complicated relationship. Finally, the systematic review acknowledges the limitations of the study and also the limitations of the cross-sectional design as cross-sectional studies only indicate that there is a connection between social media use and mental health, but are unable to point out the direction of that connection. (Keles, McCrae, and Grealish 2020, p.82ff)

One of the most used social media platforms and also one of the most researched and studied for a connection with mental health is without doubt Facebook (Pew Research Center 2018) (Schønning et al. 2020). Limiting Facebook use for a week has significant positive effects on psychological health and life satisfaction. That is demonstrated by an experiment done in Denmark in 2015 (Tromholt 2016). Another study using experience sampling investigated the relationship between the social media platform Facebook and the psychological well-being of young adults. The study measured the current mental states of the participants at different intervals throughout the day. Results clearly show how Facebook worsened both short-term and long term psychological health. Excessive screen time on the platform was connected to worsened mental health at the next measured interval and also caused lower life satisfaction after two weeks (Kross et al. 2013).

Most of the studies in the field investigate the relationship between social media and negative mental health outcomes, while there appears to be less emphasis on the association between social media and positive mental health outcomes. Finally, only a few studies observe the different types of social media usage (Schønning et al. 2020, p.11).

3.1.2. Current Research on Screen Time and Mental Health

Screen time is a phenomenon closely connected to social media and researched for potential effects on mental health. For example, several cross-sectional studies have proposed screen time as a factor in worsening young people's mental health (Tang et al. 2021, p.1). However, the cross-sectional design is often limited in determining a given relationship's causal direction. That is why longitudinal studies exploring screen time and mental health outcomes are critical (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.10). A systematic review from 2021 tried to summarise existing longitudinal research to better explain the connection between screen time and mental health problems. The review used several databases for longitudinal research articles published before August 2020. The final sample consisted of 35 longitudinal studies. According to the review, the most obvious connection between screen time and following mental health outcomes was between screen time and depression, compared to the relationship between screen time and other mental health issues. However, the link between screen time and depressive outcomes differed depending on the device and how it was used (the type of screen time usage) and the connection was stronger for screen time spent on smartphones and computers, compared to screen time spent watching tv or video-gaming. The review also found a stronger association between screen time and following depression than the opposite association (between depression and increased screen time). Once again, the connections found were “small to very small in size” (Tang et al. 2021, p.12).

However, findings from several longitudinal studies suggest that excessive screen time is associated with worse psychological and mental health in both children and adolescents. A longitudinal study found strong associations between recreational screen time and different mental health outcomes (Babic et al. 2017). An Australian longitudinal study found a linkage between screen-based sedentary behaviour and the emergence of psychological disorders in children. Over the course of two years, the study discovered that excessive usage of screen-based devices was associated with the “development of emotional symptoms in young children” and also led to hyperactivity and behavioural problems in older ones (Allen and Vella 2015).

Life satisfaction can also be influenced by different screen time activities, according to a longitudinal study set in Germany. The study explored data from the German Family Panel, a nationwide randomly sampled longitudinal study, consisting of more than 12, 000 participants. Findings suggest that social activities, such as meeting with friends, sports or holiday trips are all have a positive effect on life satisfaction while

using the internet recreationally and watching television both influence life satisfaction negatively (Schmiedeberg and Schröder 2017, p.5ff).

Studies also demonstrate a complicated relationship between screen time and psychological well-being. A relationship that goes in both directions (excessive screen time causing worsening of the mental health and worse mental health causing excessive screen time). However, regardless of the direction of the relationship, those findings have important implications in terms of early diagnosing and treatment of mental health illnesses. Adolescents and preadolescents with excessive screen time usage could be identified as a risk group for developing mental health and psychological problems and therefore could be closely examined and measures can be taken to prevent the onset of potential symptoms (Twenge and Campbell 2018, p.281) (Gunnell et al. 2016).

Screen time is often connected with electronic media use, such as television viewing, computer gaming or computer usage. The focus of a longitudinal study is exactly the relationship between child's electronic media usage and their well-being. Findings suggest that excessive use of electronic media is connected to and predicts worse well-being. A total of 16 864 children from 8 European countries participated and there was a 2-year follow-up. Although findings differed by gender and activity, the association were consistent. For example, watching TV both during workdays and during the weekend is connected to worse well-being compared to screen time spent gaming. (Hinkley et al. 2014, p.3f)

3.1.3. Screen Time and Brain Development

Screen time could influence the development of the brain both positively and negatively. Prolonged intervals of screen time (more than 2-3 hours), that are spent in front of a television, computer or mobile device can influence the neurological development, as well as the brain chemistry of adolescents' brains. (Neophytou, Manwell, and Eikelboom 2021, p.725). This in turn can disrupt the healthy functioning of the brain and affect cognitive, physical and emotional development and therefore general wellbeing. Early and prolonged use of electronic devices and media is linked to a higher risk of adverse mental health symptoms, such as hyperactivity, attention deficits, anxiety and depression (Maras et al. 2015) and since the beginning of the century children are being introduced to television much earlier compared to children born in the 1970s (Christakis and Zimmerman 2006) (Zimmerman, Christakis, and Meltzoff 2007).

Infants and toddlers exposed to television are also at risk because the brain regions, responsible for language and vocabulary development are strongly influenced by the type of television. For example, child TV shows such as *Dora the Explorer* which expect active participation from their viewers led to an increased lexicon and verbal abilities of the children. With shows such as *Teletubbies*, however, language learning in newborns and toddlers was considerably hampered (Linebarger and Walker 2005, p.5ff).

Excessive screen time can also influence the learning and memory of toddlers. A longitudinal study with two consecutive follow-ups (after one and after three years) explored the effects of weekly hours of screen time on two-year-olds. Findings suggest that higher amounts (more hours) of screen time are strongly linked to lower scores on cognitive tests, done in the follow-ups. During the first five years of the child's life, the development is tremendous. The study investigated the child's developmental outcomes during that vital stage of life and it discovered that screen time can have an impact on children's capacity to develop properly (Madigan et al. 2019, p.2ff).

The Internet can be another source of screen time and therefore can influence the development of the brain. Internet addiction causes changes in the thickness of the orbitofrontal cortex, which are very similar to changes caused by drug and behavioural addictions. Male adolescents, diagnosed with internet addiction had a considerable reduction in cortical thickness compared to healthy males. It is suggested that this would make them predisposed to addiction-related behaviour and could play a critical role in their reward system and decision-making. The study findings indicate that internet addiction and other types of addictions share the same characteristics and the same "neurobiological marker of addiction-related disorders" (Hong et al. 2013).

3.2. Hypothesis

The findings from the current systematic review are expected to present definitive results for the connection between screen time and mental health and the association between social media and mental health and mixed results about the direction of those connections and associations. This hypothesis is based on discoveries and effects explored in previous systematic reviews, longitudinal studies, meta-analyses and scoping reviews. The cross-sectional design is expected to be predominant among the study designs. According to findings from a scoping review, the majority of the studies in the field are using a cross-sectional design and most of them are focusing on the negative mental health implications of social media. Depression is the mental health condition that is researched the most

(Schønning et al. 2020). It is expected that only a few longitudinal studies, exploring the current topic are going to be discovered and therefore discussed in this paper. Exactly studies with longitudinal design are the main objective and the main argument of this review because, unlike cross-sectional studies, they could present the direction of a given connection, which in the case of exploring social media and screen time effects on mental health is of great importance (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019, p.78).

This review is going to explore and point out different reoccurring key themes in the studies found to be relevant and discuss their weaknesses, as well as their strengths. Finally, this review is going to summarize the findings and will give recommendations for future research.

4. Method and Data

Social media and screen time are relatively new phenomena, and the possible links between them and mental health have not yet been extensively researched (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019). Worldwide, many systematic studies investigating mental health outcomes have been conducted. However, the available literature heavily focuses on mental health alone so social media from the perspective of social science and the connection between social media and screen time with mental health is the main topic of only a few studies (Alonzo et al. 2021). Therefore, a paper that pays closer attention to the recent findings in this area is needed. More precisely, a scientific text that can summarize the recent findings, evaluate them, and draw conclusions about the social media ecology (Zhao, Lampe, and Ellison 2016) and how it correlates with psychological health. This paper aims to systematically review, analyze, and discuss the relevant literature and recognize and name the gaps in the current research by closely inspecting the relationship between social media, screen time, and mental health.

Systematic reviews have the most significant potential of giving the most trustworthy and diverse information about the given topic. That is, of course, true when they are conducted correctly and in accordance with ethical principles. The researcher's goal is to find relevant literature, analyze it and draw conclusions about the research question and research topic. In addition, a systematic review will provide information about the decision-making process, which includes the questions on which the review is based, inclusion and exclusion criteria for the studies and the methodology used during the research (Petrosino et al. 2001).

This review contributes to the research field of social media, screen time and mental health research by focusing on and summarizing previous findings. It could be an assistance to researchers and present them with a complete view of existing literature. Findings from the review provide insight into the extent to which researchers can critically analyze the connection between social media screen time and mental health and understand concerns that need to be addressed by scientists in the future. The current systematic review was based on the main research question: What are the effects of social media and screen time on mental health?

4.1. Search strategy

The research was conducted to identify studies analyzing the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health. In order to do that, several different databases were explored and evaluated, and finally, the database PubMed was chosen as a source of relevant literature and the best match for the topic that had to be researched. The search of the database PubMed consisted of several steps. First, several searches were performed using different keywords to get an overall idea about the relevant literature. Keywords and keyword combinations implemented in the search strategy were: 1. social media, 2. screen time, 3. mental health, 4. social media AND mental health, 5. screen time AND mental health, 6. ((social media OR screen time) AND mental health). Next, the search was limited to peer-reviewed, full-text research papers from the past five years in the English language that had included in the title the terms *social media* or *screen time* in combination with *mental health*. Table 1 presents the keyword combinations, the database and the number of results found for each search.

Keyword	Database	Number of results
social media[Title]	PubMed	4,766
screen time[Title]	PubMed	618
mental health[Title]	PubMed	23,922
(social media[Title]) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	136

(screen time[Title]) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	16
((social media[Title]) OR (screen time[Title])) AND (mental health[Title])	PubMed	150

Table 1: Keyword combination, database, and number of results

4.2. Study selection

The first three searches resulted in a total of 29 306 articles. The majority of the articles were not relevant to the research and lacked the relationship between mental health and social media or screen time. In order to narrow the search to more results relevant to the research topic, the search strategy was adjusted. Several searches focusing on the relationship between social media and mental health or on the relationship between screen time and mental health were performed.

Based on the second part of the results in Table 1., a total of 302 relevant articles were found. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 153 duplicate articles were found and therefore removed. Out of the 149 articles left, 71 citations passed the inclusion criteria and were selected for screening. After the abstract and full-text screening, another 26, respectively, 2 articles were excluded. Finally, a total of 43 citations were included for the purposes of this review. The following PRISMA Flow Diagram presents the whole process of inclusion and exclusion in detail:

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram

5. Results

The result section of this paper will introduce the methodology used in the selected literature and will give an overview of the results. Finally, all the results will be organized according to key themes and will be systematically presented.

5.1. Study Methodologies

The 43 included articles differed by choice of research method, as fourteen of the studies were cross-sectional, twelve were reviews (review articles, systematic reviews, umbrella reviews), and seven of the included articles chose the longitudinal design. In addition, there were four quantitative and three qualitative studies, one Specification Curve Analysis, a Meta-Analysis and a Randomized Controlled Trial included in this paper. Table 2 illustrates and summarises the methodology of all the forty-three included articles.

Method	Number of studies
Cross-Sectional	14
Review	12
Longitudinal	7
Quantitative	4
Qualitative	3
Specification Curve Analysis	1
Randomized Controlled Trial	1
Meta-Analysis	1

Table 2: Methodology of the included articles

5.2. Summary of the results

The results present findings of adverse social media effects on mental health, such as depression, anxiety, and self-harm; different negative social effects such as fear of missing out, social comparison and low self-esteem, potential social media benefits in terms of mental health, the connection between screen time and mental health and finally,

the mediating effects in the relationship between social media, screen time and different mental health outcomes. A full summary of the findings of all the included articles could be found in Table 3 in the appendix.

5.3. Key Themes

The following chapter explores the key themes that were identified during the literature analysis. The key themes that reappeared and were repeated in the included studies and throughout the research are as follows: Potential Social Media benefits on Mental Health, Screen Time and Mental Health, Adverse Social Media Effects on Mental Health and Mediating Effects in the relationship between Social Media, Screen Time and Mental Health. The studies dealing with the same topics are reviewed and analysed together so that their findings, statements and views can be compared and later discussed. A complete overview of the studies and the key themes is illustrated in Table 4:

	Social Media Benefits	Social Media Adverse Effects				Screen Time and Mental Health
		Depression	Anxiety	Social Effects	Self-Harm	
Number of Studies	11	13	4	5	6	9

Table 4: Overview of the Key Themes

5.3.1. Potential benefits

Eleven articles suggested a possible positive effect of social media on mental health in some way. Out of the eleven studies, one was cross-sectional (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019), one was a randomised controlled trial (Muniswamy et al. 2021), one was longitudinal (Lu et al. 2020), five were reviews (Srivastava et al. 2019) (Karim et al. 2020) (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020) (Nesi 2020) (Sarangi et al. 2022). Finally, three of the articles were qualitative studies (Latha et al. 2020) (O'Reilly 2020) (O'Reilly et al. 2019). The studies differed in method and data and researched different spectrums of potential benefits of social media, and therefore the results varied. For example, while some investigated what kind of social media behaviour exactly is triggering mental health outcomes (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019), other studies explored the potential of social media in promoting mental health (O'Reilly et al. 2019) (Latha et al. 2020).

A randomised controlled trial explored the possibility of an intervention based on one of the social media platforms to influence software engineers' mental and physical health. The social platform of choice was Facebook, and sixty individuals were divided into intervention and control groups for two months. The study found a significant reduction of sitting time during work hours by almost an hour in the intervention group. In addition, the authors reported remarkable differences between anxiety, depression, and stress scores (Muniswamy et al. 2021).

A cross-sectional study conducted on one thousand and twenty-seven American adults found that social media use as part of a routine and in the absence of emotional connection to the social media platform has a positive impact on mental health outcomes. The article presents social media as a fundamental part of people's behaviour and states that social media creates an emotional connection that future research should, by all means, consider (Bekalu, McCloud, and Viswanath 2019).

Social media platforms as a ground for mental health movements are another potential benefit because the structure of the platforms allows for a quick flow of information between users in a short period (Latha et al. 2020, p.5). Another advantage of social media in mental health promotion is that social media is often a source of information and a tool that helps adolescents unwind. This widespread social media presence opens doors for ways to support and encourage psychological health (O'Reilly et al. 2019).

A qualitative study explored three different social media campaigns on social media platforms Instagram and Facebook for five months. The study found that to reach more people, educate, and boost mental health, Facebook groups are a more successful way than Instagram pages. Aside from the low cost and "high scalability" of mental health campaigns based on social media, other positives include the options of self-tracking and customised feedback (Latha et al. 2020).

Social media usage on people with existing mental health conditions is a topic of a recent study. Specifically, the study investigated people suffering from depression and how different user actions on social media positively and negatively affect that particular mental health condition. The findings indicate that trust, a sense of shared identity, and emotional and informational support are among the positive effects social media has on depression. However, the number of social media interactions affected depression negatively. Shared identity and trust had more significant positive effects on females than

males, while the number of social media interactions affected female users more negatively than they did affect male users (Lu et al. 2020).

In another qualitative study, a focus group of eight mental health professionals was interviewed about their opinion on different sides of social media. Findings suggest that people with mental health disorders, usually subject to isolation, may benefit from the sense of connectedness and social media-induced communication, therefore equating their social development with that of their peers and may be a prerequisite for reduced isolation (O'Reilly 2020).

A systematic review from 2020 (Karim et al. 2020) investigated the relationship between social media and mental health. Out of the sixteen articles reviewed, only three explored the topic of potential social media benefits on mental health. The current review discusses two of them (O'Reilly 2020) (O'Reilly et al. 2019). The third article presented a social media marketing strategy for overall health promotion (Mehmet, Roberts, and Nayeem 2020).

Another systematic review from the same year (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020) looked at the effects of social media on mental health. The review included sixteen studies, separated into three groups according to their effects (positive, negative, neutral). A total of five articles suggested positive social media effects on mental health, and the included studies investigated social media effects on four different platforms: Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and MySpace (2020). The most notable finding was the positive effect of social relationships on the social platform Facebook, which repeated the critical theme of social connectedness (Neubaum and Krämer 2015).

Several review articles also explored potential social media benefits on mental health (Nesi 2020) (Srivastava et al. 2019). The findings again focus on social relationships (Anderson and Jiang 2018), opportunities for entertainment, identity development and creative expression (2018). In addition, the need to present oneself online and the feeling to belong, together with self-worth and compassion, are important reasons for the positive influence of social media (Toma and Hancock 2013) (Nadkarni and Hofmann 2012). Finally, another review article presented the opportunity of social media to improve mental health in a post-pandemic world after the events and consequences of Covid-19. Positives of social media in such situations include information about current events, vaccination promotion and support for disabled people (Sarangi et al. 2022).

5.3.2. Screen time and mental health

Nine articles focused on the relationship between screen time and mental health outcomes. Out of the nine articles, six were cross-sectional (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018) (Smith et al. 2020) (Raza et al. 2021) (Twenge and Farley 2021) (Woo et al. 2021) (Barthorpe et al. 2020), two implemented the longitudinal design (Nigg et al. 2021) (Paulich et al. 2021) and one article was a systematic review of longitudinal studies (Tang et al. 2021).

A cross-sectional study from 2018, set in Reykjavík, Iceland, investigated the effects of screen time and physical activity on adolescents' mental health. Reports were collected from the participants using a survey poll that included questions about weekly physical activity, screen time hours per day and mental health conditions. Options for mental health status included symptoms of anxiety and depression and also questions about self-esteem and life satisfaction (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018, p.3f). In addition, wrist-worn accelerometers measured the physical activity of the participants. The final sample consisted of 244 participants, 100 of whom were boys. The results showed that reports of less screen time were associated with a seriously lower risk of reporting anxiety, depression, dissatisfaction with life or low self-esteem. Finally, participants who reported less screen time combined with more physical activity had a significantly lower risk of experiencing adverse mental health outcomes than the group reporting more screen time and less physical activity (2018, p.7f).

A longitudinal study also researched screen time combined with physical activity and its relationship to mental health. Six hundred eighty-six children participated between 2003 and 2017 for a total period of 11 years. The study aimed to investigate the association of physical activity and screen time with mental health outcomes. Emotional indicators, behavioural issues, hyperactivity, peer connections, prosocial behaviour, and overall strengths and problems characterized mental health. The results show that irrespective of gender, physical activity declines, and screen time grows as participants age (Nigg et al. 2021, p.220). The findings suggest that physical activity and screen time have little to no connection and must be inspected independently (2021, p. 224f). Finally, the results showed a consistent link between screen time and mental health; however, this varied with gender. Screen time negatively affected the self-reported mental health of females, both preadolescents and adolescents (2021, p. 226).

Cross-sectional research looked at screen time and mental health outcomes. The study comprised 932 individuals, and half of the participants were between 35 and 64

years old. In the entire sample, the results revealed a positive connection between screen usage per day in hours and poor mental health. Furthermore, the relationship between daily screen usage and poor mental health was significant, especially among women and adults aged 35–64 years old, independent of gender (Smith et al. 2020, p.1).

Eleven thousand four hundred twenty-seven adolescents participated in a cross-sectional study done in the United Kingdom. The study investigated how four specific screen time activities (social media, gaming, internet and television) connect to four different types of mental health measures (depressive symptoms, life satisfaction, self-harm and self-esteem). The results suggest that some screen-based activities correlate more strongly with poor mental health than others. For example, social media and internet use were more strictly related to all four mental health indicators than gaming and television (Twenge and Farley 2021, p.207).

A recent longitudinal study from the United States also explored how screen time is associated with mental health. The study's final sample consisted of 11,875 children between nine and ten years old. Screen time and mental health were researched with behavioural issues, academic performance, sleep habits, and peer relationships (Paulich et al. 2021, p. 3ff). The findings suggest that more significant screen usage is related to poorer mental health, more conduct disorders, lower academic achievement, and worse sleep hygiene. Peer relationships, however, benefited from more screen time (2021, p. 16f).

A systematic review of longitudinal studies included thirty-five longitudinal articles. Findings suggest that the relationship between screen time and depression is small, while different devices and uses moderate that relationship. In addition, the review found no evidence to support the association between anxiety and self-esteem longitudinally. Finally, the study evaluates the impact of excessive screen time on the mental health of young adults as "negligible or small" (Tang et al. 2021, p.1).

The screen time and smartphone use habits of South Korean adolescents were the focus of a recent cross-sectional study. 54,243 participants answered questions about their smartphone use, hours of screen time and four mental health indicators (depression, sleep, suicidal symptoms and stress). The use of smartphones was divided into two groups: social- and nonsocial interaction, and screen time per day was split up into four groups: less than two hours, two hours or more, less than four hours, and four hours or more. Results showed that all four mental health indicators were severely affected on weekdays by participants who used smartphones four or more hours per day, irrespective of the type

of use (social or nonsocial). At the same time, social or nonsocial types of use influenced the mental health outcomes for participants who used their smartphones for two or more but less than four hours. The findings suggest that the type of screen time usage seriously affects the possible mental health outcomes (Woo et al. 2021, p.1426).

A time-use diary study also found a relationship between social screen time use and mental health outcomes. The study analysed cross-sectional data from the Millennium Cohort Study to find patterns and relationships between social media screen time and three leading mental health outcomes: depression, self-harm and self-esteem (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.4f). Similar findings were extracted from the study for weekday and weekend social media screen time. Increased screen time on social media resulted in a rise in all three mental health outcomes(2020, p.6f). Finally, the study also acknowledges the limitation of the cross-sectional model (2020, p.1).

Screen time spent during binge-watching was researched for impact on mental health. A cross-sectional study included 1089 people aged 18 and above who took an online survey regarding binge-watching on one of the streaming sites. The study's findings show that excessive binge-watching on platforms such as Netflix, Amazon Prime, and Disney Plus is linked to negative mental health consequences such as sleeplessness, stress, loneliness, anxiety, and depression (Raza et al. 2021, p.1626).

5.3.3. Adverse effects

The majority of the included studies explore different negative mental health outcomes, caused by social media, or the connection between those outcomes and social media. A total of thirty-two articles investigated some kind of adverse social media effects on mental health. The most common mental health issues associated with social media are depression, social media and anxiety, social media and adverse social effects (self-esteem, fear of missing out, social comparisons/ focus on self-presentation) and finally social media connection to self-harm related behaviour.

A specification curve analysis found that the link between social media use and mental health is significant and persistent among girls (Twenge et al. 2022), and several systematic reviews suggest that social media and different mental health outcomes are connected (Karim et al. 2020) (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020) (Alonzo et al. 2021).

However, a longitudinal study from 2021 with a two-year follow-up found no long-term connection between frequent social media use and mental health issues.

Instead, the study suggests that social media may signal potential mental health outcomes instead of being a cause for such (Beeres et al. 2021, p.959).

An umbrella review the same year reported mixed results after researching and closely investigating seven meta-analyses, nine systematic reviews, and nine narrative reviews. The reported connection between social media and mental health differed between small and substantial. The authors explain that phenomenon with the differences in the interpretation approaches of results (Valkenburg, Meier, and Beyens 2021, p.60ff).

Different results are also a consequence of different definitions of social media and mental health and research methods (2021, p.60f). Therefore, the current review will explore the research methods used by the researchers, the key themes that were repeated in various articles and, of course, the different results and interpretations of the relationship between social media and mental health.

5.3.3.1. Social media and depression

Thirteen articles explored the connection between social media and depression or depressive symptoms. Out of the thirteen articles, eight were cross-sectional (Barthorpe et al. 2020) (Fardouly et al. 2020) (Young, Kolubinski, and Frings 2020) (Lin et al. 2021) (Malaeb et al. 2021) (Skogen et al. 2021) (Sujarwoto, Saputri, and Yumarni 2021) (Twenge and Farley 2021), two were quantitative studies (Fardouly et al. 2018) (Barry et al. 2017), one was longitudinal (Kelly et al. 2018). Finally, one was a meta-analysis (Huang 2022).

A cross-sectional study found that increased time spent on social media for females related to an increase in the number of depressive symptoms. Those findings were consistent for both weekday and weekend use. The relationship between males' social media screen time and depressive symptoms was insignificant (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.6).

An Australian cross-sectional study focused on preadolescents' social media use and mental health. The findings indicate that more time spent on YouTube is associated with increased depressive symptoms (Fardouly et al. 2020, p.12) and that appearance investment forecasts signs of depression (2020, p.13).

Findings from another study suggest that the attachment style of individuals plays a significant role in regulating the relationship between social media and mental health. For example, participants who reported avoiding attachment or feeling uncomfortable with intimacy had higher depression scores (Young, Kolubinski, and Frings 2020, p.5).

According to the findings of another cross-sectional study, problematic social media use is associated with depression (Lin et al. 2021, p.165). Initially, the study investigated if generalized trust and perceived social support mediate the relationship between problematic social media use and mental health outcomes. Additionally, the findings suggest that generalized trust and perceived social support can alleviate the effects of problematic social media on depressive states (2021, p.170)

Other potential mediators of this relationship were also investigated. A cross-sectional study explored stress as a possible influencer of the association between problematic social media use and depression (Malaeb et al. 2021). Greater levels of stress were shown to be strongly related to higher levels of depression, and greater problematic social media use was substantially linked to higher depression when stress was absent from the model. However, the connection between problematic social media use and depression was insignificant when stress was included (2021, p.4).

Cross-sectional research done in Norway revealed the following findings: focusing on self-presentation on social media platforms is associated with depression (Skogen et al. 2021, p.1). The final sample consisted of 513 participants with an average age of 17.1 years. The study explored the connection between self-presentation on social media platforms and mental health outcomes (2021, p.10)

Findings from another research also underlined the importance of problematic social media and symptoms of depression. The study investigated university students in Indonesia cross-sectionally and discovered that students with a higher level of social dependence were more likely to suffer from moderate depression (Sujarwoto, Saputri, and Yumarni 2021, p.7).

Monitoring how often people check their social media profiles is also connected with social media addiction and problematic social media behaviour. For example, a study reports that the frequency of checking social media platforms, as reported by adolescents, is strongly associated with depressive symptoms reported by the parents (Barry et al. 2017, p.6).

Social media effects are not necessarily direct. Findings from a longitudinal study using data from UKMillenniumCohort Study suggest that increased social media usage is associated with online harassment, poor sleep, low self-esteem, and poor body image. All of these indicators are associated with higher scores of depression. Similar indirect connections are observed for increased social media use, body dissatisfaction and depressive symptoms. One-third of the participants who use social media for more than

5 hours per day were more prone to being unhappy with their bodies, and body dissatisfaction was directly connected to depressive states (Kelly et al. 2018, p.62ff).

Finally, a meta-analysis exploring the connection between social media and mental health outcomes reveals that the average association between problematic social media usage and depression is moderate (Huang 2022, p.16ff).

5.3.3.2. Social media and anxiety

Four cross-sectional studies (Skogen et al. 2021) (Malaeb et al. 2021) (Lin et al. 2021) (Young, Kolubinski, and Frings 2020) and one quantitative study (Barry et al. 2017) explored anxiety as a mental health outcome and possible adverse effect of social media.

The number of adolescents' social media accounts and the frequency of checking those accounts notably correlate with anxiety symptoms (Barry et al. 2017, p.6). Those are the findings of a study from the United States that focused on adolescents' mental health connection to social media. Parents and adolescents participated together and reported about adolescents' social media profiles, activity and mental health outcomes (2017).

The general use of social media was found to be positively associated with anxiety (Lin et al. 2021, p.168) and problematic social media use correlated significantly with anxiety (Malaeb et al. 2021, p.4). In addition, a cross-sectional study suggests that focus on self-presentation as social media behaviour is connected firmly to anxiety symptoms (Skogen et al. 2021, p.6f).

A cross-sectional study from 2021 linked problematic social media behaviour with increased anxiety symptoms. The final sample of the study consisted of 466 young Lebanese participants. The study investigated the potential mediating effects of stress on the relationship between social media and mental health outcomes. The findings demonstrate a clear link between excessive social media use and anxiety symptoms, both when stress is present and when it is not.(Malaeb et al. 2021, p.4f).

Finally, findings from yet another cross-sectional study showed the association between focusing on social media appearance, self-presentation and anxiety symptoms. The study was conducted in Norway and included 513 senior high school students, 58% of whom were male. Facebook, Instagram and TikTok were the platforms most connected with a focus on self-presentation (Skogen et al. 2021, p.10f) and, therefore, anxiety symptoms and the strength of the connection between focus on social media self-presentation and anxiety were significant (2021, p.1).

5.3.3.3. Social Media and social effects

The most common connections between social media and adverse social effects researched are social media and fear of missing out, social media and self-esteem and social media and self-presentation. All three of them indirectly influence mental health (Beyens, Frison, and Eggermont 2016) (Barthorpe et al. 2020) (Vogel et al. 2015, p.252f). A total of five articles explore the relationship between social media and self-esteem, social media, and fear of missing out and social media and social comparisons. Out of the six articles, three were cross-sectional (Barthorpe et al. 2020) (Fardouly et al. 2020) (Skogen et al. 2021), one was a quantitative study (Barry et al. 2017), and one was a review article (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020).

A cross-sectional study found a connection between focus on self-presentation and symptoms of anxiety and depression. The final sample consisted of 513 participants, and findings suggest that the participants who were more engaged with self-presentation on social media were more likely to have symptoms of anxiety (Skogen et al. 2021, p.7) Regular comparison of social media appearance and the perception of others being more attractive than oneself is linked to lower satisfaction with the body, higher probability of an eating disorder, more symptoms of depression and more significant social anxiety (Fardouly et al. 2020, p.12).

Moreover, the number of adolescents' social media accounts and the frequency with which they checked their profiles are significantly associated with experiences of fear of missing out and loneliness (Barry et al. 2017, p.6). Those are the findings of another study, including 113 pairs of parents and adolescents who participated together (2017, p.1).

A review article also commented on the possibility of social media affecting adolescents' self-image and relationships (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020, p.136). For example, social media-induced social comparisons or negative interactions could have a harmful impact on anxiety, depression and well-being (Seabrook, Kern, and Rickard 2016, p.8).

Finally, another cross-sectional study included the relationship between social media screen time and self-esteem in its research. Findings illustrate how social media screen time of females significantly correlates with lower self-esteem. However, minimal evidence about social media screen time and self-esteem connection was found in men (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.6f).

5.3.3.4. Social media and self-harm

Six articles include the relationship between self-harm and social media in their research. Out of the six studies, four are cross-sectional (Twenge and Farley 2021) (Bailey et al. 2022) (Woo et al. 2021) (Barthorpe et al. 2020), one is a quantitative study (Berryman, Ferguson, and Negy 2018), and one is a review article (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020).

In a cross-sectional study done in the United Kingdom, 11,427 participants aged 13 to 15 answered if they have hurt themselves in the past year with yes or no. The study explored the relationship between four different screen time activities and mental health outcomes such as self-harm. The results suggest that excessive social media and internet use (more than five hours per day) are strongly connected to boys' self-harm-related behaviour. However, the association between gaming and television and self-harm was small. At the same time, social media became problematic and therefore connected to self-harm for girls after more than two hours per day. (Twenge and Farley 2021, p.213f). A more significant proportion of social media time during weekdays is linked to a higher risk of self-harm by females, according to another study done in 2020 (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.6)

The results of another cross-sectional study done in South Korea showed that indicators related to suicide (suicide ideation, suicide plan, suicide attempts history) were severely affected on weekdays by participants who used smartphones for four or more hours per day (Woo et al. 2021, p.1422). The article focused on adolescents' screen time and smartphone connection with different mental health outcomes. The participants answered questions about their daily smartphone use and different mental health outcomes. (2021, p.1421).

Posting provocative social media updates in order to cause worry in friends and family (vaguebooking) is connected to both loneliness and suicidal thoughts, according to a quantitative study (Berryman, Ferguson, and Negy 2018).

Findings from a cross-sectional study set in Australia also suggest a link between suicidal behaviour or self-harm and social media platforms. The study included adolescents who responded anonymously to an online survey. The article had the goal of investigating the mental health of Australians aged 16-25 and the social media impact. Almost half of the participants (51/118) stated that they had experiences with social media

websites that are "unhelpful or harmful" in terms of suicide or self-harm related thoughts, with Tumblr being the most listed as such platform (Bailey et al. 2022, p.8).

Finally, a review article summarized the possibilities of social media promoting, romanticizing, and normalizing self-harm (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020).

5.3.4. Mediators

During the process of analysing relevant literature, several mediators were identified. Gender, Cyberbullying, Sleep, Physical activity and the Covid-19 pandemic were all found to influence the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health in some way.

5.3.4.1. Social Media and Cyberbullying

Six articles investigated social media cyberbullying and its potential connection with mental health. Out of them, one was longitudinal (Viner et al. 2019), and the rest were review articles (Srivastava et al. 2019) (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020) (Nesi 2020) (Flynn, Mote, and Morse 2022) and a scoping review (Schønning et al. 2020).

The scoping review included thirteen articles connected with social media and cyberbullying (Schønning et al. 2020, p.8). Findings suggest that cyberbullying is simply "a new tool to harm victims already bullied by traditional means" (Wolke, Lee, and Guy 2017, p.899) and that both male and female victims of cyberbullying are more prone to feel unwell psychologically (Kim et al. 2018, p.4ff).

A longitudinal study from 2019 explored the effects of social media on mental health and the potential mediating impact of cyberbullying on the relationship (Viner et al. 2019). Initially, the study conducted a secondary analysis on data from another national representative longitudinal study. The final sample consisted of 12 886 adolescents aged between 13 and 16 in England. The findings suggest a connection between frequent social media use and adverse mental health outcomes. However, those associations are significantly influenced by cyberbullying in females. Finally, the research illustrates that the facilitation of cyberbullying is one of the primary triggers of the adverse effects of extensive social media use (2019, p.694).

The four review articles report similar findings on cyberbullying, its connection to social media and its relationship with mental health outcomes. For example, Cyberbullying victims often experience poor self-esteem, and they often lack confidence. In addition, loneliness, insomnia, and depressive and anxiety symptoms are also experienced by victims of cyberbullying (Hinduja and Patchin 2008) (Srivastava et al.

2019). Finally, cyberbullying is associated with self-harm and suicidal behaviours (John et al. 2018) (Nesi 2020).

5.3.4.2. Social Media and Sleep

Six articles explored the connection between social media screen time and sleep. Out of the six articles, one was a longitudinal study (Viner et al. 2019, p.4), one was a systematic review (Alonzo et al. 2021), two were cross-sectional (Woo et al. 2021) (Malaeb et al. 2021), and two were review articles (Nesi 2020) (Abi-Jaoude, Naylor, and Pignatiello 2020).

A systematic review, including 28 cross-sectional and five cohort studies, investigated the relationship between social media use, sleep quality, and mental health issues. More than half of the articles found that sleep quality was connected to active use of social media and mental health. Two-thirds of the cross-sectional studies found solid and essential links between excessive social media usage and mental health issues. The majority of the longitudinal studies found the frequency of social media usage to be a risk factor for poor sleep and poor mental health. More than half of the cohort studies reported that sleep quality mediates the relationship between social media use and mental health issues (Alonzo et al. 2021, p.366).

The mediating effects of sleep on the social media and mental health correlation are explored by another longitudinal study from 2019. The study also researched cyberbullying and physical activity as potential impacts on the relationship. The findings suggest that excessive social media use links to adverse mental health effects, irrespective of sex. However, the relationship among females was strongly influenced by the quantity of sleep (less than eight hours were determined as insufficient). The research demonstrates how insufficient sleep in combination with a high frequency of social media use may be detrimental to adolescents' health (Viner et al. 2019, p.694).

More than four hours of social interactions (which include social media) with the smartphone is found to be associated with sleep dissatisfaction by a cross-sectional study (Woo et al. 2021, p.1422f). Another cross-sectional study reported a strong connection between insomnia and depression (Malaeb et al. 2021, p.4). The study also found an association between problematic social media use and insomnia, which was strong when the model did not include stress. However, the association between problematic social media and insomnia was not significant when stress was included. Finally, the study

concludes that stress mediates the relationship between problematic social media usage and insomnia (2021, p.5).

5.3.4.3. Screen Time and Physical Activity

Screen time is often connected with sedentary behaviour and less physical activity. Because of that the research on screen time and mental health connections should be supplemented by research on physical activity as a potential mediator of this relationship. A study set in Iceland explored how physical activity could influence the relationship between screen time and negative mental health outcomes. The data was gathered via a survey poll that included questions regarding weekly physical activity, daily screen use, and mental health issues. Anxiety and depression symptoms, as well as questions regarding self-esteem and life satisfaction, were among the options for mental health status and the individuals' physical activity was monitored using wrist-worn accelerometers (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018, p.3f). Findings illustrate that participants who reported less screen time and greater physical activity had a decreased chance of having negative mental health outcomes than those who reported more screen time and less physical activity. The findings also imply that reporting less screen usage was linked to a significantly decreased likelihood of anxiety, sadness, life dissatisfaction, or low self-esteem. Furthermore, the individuals' reports of physical activity revealed similar findings, even though the measured physical activity did not appear to be linked to any mental health condition. (2018, p.7f).

Physical activity and screen time have little to no association, according to the findings of a longitudinal study, and must be considered separately (Nigg et al. 2021, p.224f). The focus of the research was screen time combined with physical activity and its relationship to mental health. Between 2003 and 2017, 686 youngsters took part in the program, which lasted 11 years. The goal of the study was to see if there was a link between physical activity and screen time and mental health outcomes. Mental health was defined by emotional indicators, behavioural concerns, hyperactivity, peer connections, prosocial behaviour, and overall strengths and weaknesses any moderate to intense activity that lasted more than 60 minutes was considered physical activity and was measured using a questionnaire. Finally, this is one of the first studies to look at the links between physical activity and screen time and self-reported mental health outcomes from childhood to adolescence in a longitudinal environment. (2021, p. 226).

Finally, longitudinal research presents important findings regarding excessive social media screen time and its connection to mental health. The final sample consisted of 12 886 English teenagers. The study determined social media use as time spent on the most popular social media sites (e.g. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter), time spent on messaging platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger) or time spent on platforms, centred around “photo-sharing” (e.g. Tumblr, Snapchat). The frequency of the social media use was measured using a questionnaire and options included: “never, weekly, every few days, daily, two to three times per day, or multiple (ie, more than three) times daily”. Physical activity was defined as “physical activities such as football, aerobics, dance classes, or swimming” and was once again measured using a questionnaire (Viner et al. 2019, p.686f). Findings indicate that the connection between social media and negative mental health symptoms is influenced by insufficient or absent physical activity. (2019, p.694f)

5.3.4.4. The Covid-19 Pandemic

The Covid-19 Pandemic had an immense impact on the overall mental health of people worldwide (Pfefferbaum and North 2020) (da Silva et al. 2021). That explains the sudden rise in different scientific investigations exploring mental health outcomes during and after the pandemic. Current research is trying to determine if social media worsens mental health (Zhong et al. 2020) and if screen time is positively or negatively linked with mental health outcomes during that period (Smith et al. 2020). This paper presents the Covid-19 pandemic as part of the mediators of the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health (Haddad et al. 2021) and also as an event that influences both the mental health and the lives of millions around the globe.

Seven articles focused on social media and screen time implications on mental health during the Coronavirus pandemic. Out of the seven articles, four were cross-sectional studies (Smith et al.) (Raza et al. 2021) (Sujarwoto, Saputri, and Yumarni 2021) (Bailey et al. 2022), and one used the longitudinal design (Valdez et al. 2020). The remaining two articles were a qualitative study (Zhong et al. 2020) and a review article (Haddad et al. 2021).

One of the cross-sectional studies was conducted in the United Kingdom in March 2020 and explored screen time and mental health outcomes. The study included nine hundred and thirty-two participants, 36.1% of whom were men. More than half of the sample were participants from the age group 35-64 years. The results showed a positive

relationship between screen usage per day in hours and poor mental health in the whole sample. The link between daily screen time and poor mental health was also substantial in women and adults aged 35–64 years, regardless of gender (Smith et al. 2020).

Another cross-sectional study focused on social media addiction and its possible connection to mental health during the covid-19 pandemic. The study was set in Indonesia in 2020 and examined university students. The sample consisted of seven hundred and nine students. The findings suggested that excessive use of social media likely has a detrimental effect on the mental health of young adults, as the students there were a positive connection between the social media addiction scores of the students and the risk of experiencing mild depressive symptoms (Sujarwoto, Saputri, and Yumarni 2021).

A study set in Australia also chose the cross-sectional design. The study included young adults aged 16-25 who responded anonymously to an online survey between June and October 2020. The article had the goal of exploring the mental health of young Australians and the social media impact on it during the Covid-19 pandemic. The final sample consisted of 371 people. Almost half of the participants claimed alarming levels of depression and anxiety, while the vast majority reported increased social media screen time since the pandemic's beginning (Bailey et al. 2022). Findings suggest that excessive social media usage (more than 7 hours per day) links to greater levels of anxiety, stress, and depression (2022, p.10).

Binge-watching was also studied during the coronavirus pandemic as a problematic screen time effect on mental health. A cross-sectional study conducted in 2021 used a sample of 1089 participants aged 18 and older to participate in an online survey about binge-watching on one of the streaming platforms (Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, Hulu). The study's findings illustrate that substantial binge-watching is associated with mental health outcomes such as insomnia, stress, loneliness, anxiety, and depression (Raza et al. 2021, p.1626).

Another study from 2020 explored the effects of social media on nonpatient mental health during the outburst of Covid-19. The final sample consisted of 2185 participants from 30 provinces of China that took part in a web survey. The results suggest that mental health disorders have a complicated structure, and many external factors dictate them, and the pandemic conditions may impact people's mental health, even if they do not have a background in psychiatric conditions (Zhong et al. 2020, p.10f). Finally, the results indicate that social media is a potential factor in the relationship between mental health and the Covid-19 pandemic (2020).

A longitudinal study from 2020 investigated Twitter Data to explore the relationship between the social media platform, mental health outcomes and the Covid-19 pandemic. After analysing large data samples, the study results showed that social media usage increased during the Covid-19 pandemic. Those findings suggest that users may have implemented social media to manage loneliness and in response to isolation. (Valdez et al. 2020, p.1).

A review from 2021 attempted to summarise the existing literature covering the impact of social media on the mental health of college students. The article confirms the link between social media and mental health but draws attention to the fact that the direction of these relationships could not be categorically determined since much of the existing research is cross-sectional (Haddad et al. 2021).

6. Discussions

This study aimed to investigate the different effects of social media and screen time on people's mental health. Specifically, the purpose was to determine whether social media and screen time have a positive or negative influence on different mental health outcomes and whether age, gender, existing mental health issues, sleep and physical activity impact this relationship as a mediator. In this review, mental health outcomes were divided into two groups: positive and negative. The negative mental health outcomes, reviewed and analysed in this paper were as follows: depression, anxiety, cyberbullying, and adverse social effects such as social comparison (focus on self-presentation) and fear of missing out. Mediators in this relationship that were investigated in this review were: sleep, gender, physical activity, and the covid-19 pandemic.

The associations between social media, screen time and mental health were investigated while analysing previous relevant literature. The whole procedure of acquiring relevant studies is thoroughly explained in the Methods section of this paper. In the following, first, the findings of the selected literature will be summarized, discussed and interpreted. Then, the implications of those findings and the way they fit into the existing research will be discussed. The limitations of this study will next be considered to help make sense of the study's composition and findings. Finally, recommendations for future research will be proposed and the gap in the research will be explained.

6.1. Summary of the findings

Social media is a relatively new invention and its impact on people's mental health is yet to be discovered and explored (Barthorpe et al. 2020) (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020). With social media being part of many people's everyday lives, its implications on mental health pose an interesting question about whether or not social media is connected to different mental health outcomes. This paper tried to summarize the different ways social media and screen time influence mental health as it discusses relevant literature. The results indicate that there is an existing connection between social media and different mental health outcomes as well as between screen time and mental health. The associations vary among different activities, gender and age and are mediated by several factors (Twenge and Farley 2021). The findings demonstrate that different mental health outcomes, including depression and anxiety, are connected with social media usage or screen time activities (Barthorpe et al. 2020) (Malaeb et al. 2021, p.4f). The data also suggest a connection between social media and self-harm and social media and adverse social effects, such as fear of missing out or low self-esteem (Barry et al. 2017) (2020). There are also a few mediating factors in the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health that the included literature explores. Physical activity, sleep, stress, cyberbullying, the focus on self-presentation and the Covid-19 Pandemic all influence that relationship to a certain extent (2021) (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018) (Skogen et al. 2021) (Valdez et al. 2020) (Viner et al. 2019). Additionally, several studies point out the possibility of social media being used as a helping tool for prevention and mental health enhancement (Muniswamy et al. 2021) (Latha et al. 2020).

6.2. Interpretations

The findings of the study are consistent with previous research findings and signal a connection between both screen time and social media on one side and mental health on the other. The direction of those connections is yet unclear and is open for speculations and interpretations. The findings, similar to previous literature suggest a link between social media and some of the most popular negative mental health outcomes such as depression, anxiety and self-harm and between screen time and adverse mental health outcomes (Barthorpe et al. 2020). The results also present some potential mediators, such as sleep (Keles, McCrae, and Grealish 2020) and physical activity (Hrafnkelsdottir et al. 2018). Additionally, this paper presents some evidence that social media could be operated as a means for mental health improvement or as a tool for prevention of negative mental health outcomes (Muniswamy et al. 2021) while also acknowledging the social

benefits that social media introduces, which is also pointed out in previous research and previous systematic reviews (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020). In line with the hypothesis, diverse social media and screen time effects on mental health were identified. As previously suggested in the hypothesis, the direction of the relationship between social media and mental health and screen time and mental health cannot be determined because of the cross-sectional design which predominates the studies methodologies.

During the process of analysing the findings of the selected literature, four main key themes were identified. These are as follows: Potential benefits of social media in terms of mental health, adverse social media effects on mental health, the relationship between screen time and mental health and finally, the mediators in the relationship between screen time and mental health.

6.2.1. Potential benefits

The benefits that social media may present in terms of mental health are mainly suggestive and only a small number of the selected studies directly investigated such possibility. The main findings from those studies indicate that among the positive effects of social media on depression are trust, a sense of shared identity, and emotional and informational support (Lu et al. 2020) and that social media-based intervention and social media-based mental health campaign are effective means to influence or even boost the mental health of people with sedentary jobs (Muniswamy et al. 2021) (Latha et al. 2020).

6.2.2. Screen time and mental health

Findings in the field of screen time and mental health are diverse. The connection between screen time and different mental health outcomes is observed and implied in several cross-sectional studies (Woo et al. 2021) (Twenge and Farley 2021), while findings from two longitudinal studies suggest that screen time is not directly associated with negative mental health conditions (Nigg et al. 2021, p.224f) (Paulich et al. 2021, p.17) but also recognize some connection between screen time and self-reported mental health of adolescents (2021, p.227) and a link between total screen time and some conduct problems (2021, p.17). Finally, a systematic review of longitudinal studies states that screen time and depression have the strongest link compared to other mental health conditions and there is very limited longitudinal evidence that screen time is connected to other mental health problems such as anxiety and low self-esteem (Tang et al. 2021, p.12). This diversity of findings is possible because of the different choice of methods

used during the research and because of the diversity of mental health outcomes that were studied.

6.2.3. Adverse effects

As previously mentioned the majority of the selected literature focused on adverse mental health outcomes connected to social media. The most reviewed and researched mental health outcomes from the selected literature are depression, anxiety, adverse social effects and self-harm. The majority of the studies reporting different social media variables that are connected to depression were designed cross-sectionally (Skogen et al. 2021) (Barthorpe et al. 2020). Findings from longitudinal studies are mixed with one study reporting an association between social media and symptoms of depression (Kelly et al. 2018) but another failed to find any longitudinal confirmation of an association between excessive social media use and negative mental health outcomes (Beeres et al. 2021). Similar findings were identified for anxiety and its connection to social media. Adverse social effects caused by social media include: fear of missing out (Barry et al. 2017), low-self esteem (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.6f) and comparison (focus on self-presentation) (Skogen et al. 2021, p.11) and those connections are acknowledged by several cross-sectional studies. Finally, this review also summarizes recent findings on self-harm connection to social media where once again the majority of the research is cross-sectional and several studies present a link between social media and different self-harm indicators (2020, p.6f) (Twenge and Farley 2021, p.213f).

6.2.4. Mediators

Several mediating effects in the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health were identified during the analysis of the relevant literature. These include Cyberbullying, Sleep, Physical Activity and the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Longitudinal links between excessive use of social media and adverse mental health outcomes were strong and consistent for girls and the relationship was influenced significantly by cyberbullying (Viner et al. 2019, p.694). Sleep and physical activity also have important implications on the relationship between social media, screen time and mental health, according to the same longitudinal study and a systematic review (2019) (Alonzo et al. 2021). The findings from the longitudinal research indicate that the negative mental health outcomes linked to social media are likely caused by the online harassment that the users face on social media, the lack of physical activity or the poor sleep, both caused by social media (2019, p.694)

Finally, the Covid-19 Pandemic also influenced the relationship of users with social media, their screen time and their mental health and acted as a mediator (Haddad et al. 2021). Studies found an increased use of social media and screen time during that period (Valdez et al. 2020) (Raza et al. 2021; Smith et al. 2020). The connections found between social media, screen time and mental health during that period are once again cross-sectional and the direction of the connection can only be suggested (Bailey et al. 2022) (Sujarwoto, Saputri, and Yumarni 2021). Findings from a longitudinal research emphasize the effect of the pandemic of the populations attitude and indicate that the high social media consumption during the pandemic can be explained with the emotional states and feelings of loneliness in people, making social media use a “coping mechanism” during that period (2020, p.1)

In line with the hypothesis, the majority of the research identified as relevant is cross-sectional and a lot of cross-sectional connections between social media, screen time and mental health were recognized and systematically analysed. The longitudinal research done in the field is little and can only suggest how this complicated relationship works. Research on the mediating effects also sheds light on the problem and gives ideas for future research. Overall cross-sectional studies present a consistent connection between social media and worsened mental health and increased screen time and adverse mental health outcomes. Findings from a few longitudinal studies suggest a negative impact of social media or screen time on mental health. However, other longitudinal studies reject this claim. Finally, some studies investigate the mediating effects of this connection.

6.3. Implications

The findings of this study have important implications in the research field. First, this is one of the few literature reviews that consider social media and screen time together and therefore could present more diverse findings in terms of the relationship between social media and mental health. Social media and screen time are two interconnected concepts and social media should be observed together with excessive screen time consequences to understand the implications on mental health best. Second, the review successfully summarises the most important research done in the last five years. This paper identifies several key themes, different mental health outcomes, and the potential mediators in the complex relationship between social media, screen time and mental health, while also acknowledging the different methodology and terminology applied in the selected

articles. Additionally, the findings of this review are consistent with previous research findings (Sharma, John, and Sahu 2020) and add to it with the addition of screen time as an integral part of the social media phenomenon. Finally, this review identifies several research gaps and gives recommendations for future research that can be useful and can assist future researchers when investigating these or similar themes.

6.4. Limitations

Despite the strengths of this paper and the implications for the research field, this review is not without limitations. First, the review only analysed relevant literature, published in English, in the last five years on the PubMed database in order to summarize and discuss current findings. More studies, relevant to the research question may be available on other databases and in other languages. Additionally, literature published beyond the mentioned time frame could also have important implications for the research field. Second, as previously mentioned, the majority of the research done is cross-sectional and could not present the direction of a given relationship. It can only state if there exists a connection (Haddad et al. 2021). Furthermore among the studies, there is no consistency in the measuring of social media usage or the measuring of negative mental health outcomes. Some studies concentrate on specific mental health outcomes such as depression and anxiety, while others research overall mental health using different questionnaires. Despite that some studies have different results, studies with the same findings also interpret them differently (Twenge et al. 2022). Finally, amidst the research, a lot of mediating factors were identified, which further obstructs the summary of the results. Nonetheless, the results that this review presents in the field of research are relevant and of service for future research.

6.5. Recommendations

As previously stated, cross-sectional research is unable to distinguish the direction of a given connection. Therefore, further longitudinal research is needed to determine which is the direction of the connection between social media, screen time and mental health. Additionally, clear definitions and measurement methods are required for social media usage and mental health to bring consistency among the results and interpretations. Furthermore, more research that concentrates on a given mental health symptom or outcome would also contribute to the consistency of the research findings. Moreover, the research field will further benefit from more longitudinal research that takes into account the mediating effects such as physical activity, sleep or cyberbullying. Finally, systematic

reviews with scopes of more than 5 years will also enrich the research field and will present important findings.

7. Conclusion

This systematic review attempted to summarize the existing relevant literature, that investigates the complex influence of social media and screen time on mental health and to answer the question “What are the effects of social media and screen time on mental health?”. To best answer the research question, forty-three scientific studies were selected, closely analysed and discussed. Findings suggest, that social media and screen time effects on mental health are diverse and that social media together with screen time have a complicated relationship with mental health. Some of the literature acknowledged the positive mental health influence of social media on mental health and suggest different ways social media can be implemented in boosting or enhancing psychological health. (Muniswamy et al. 2021) (Lu et al. 2020). Findings regarding screen time and mental health connections are diverse. Cross-sectional studies indicate a clear connection (Woo et al. 2021) (Twenge and Farley 2021), while longitudinal research rejects these claims (Nigg et al. 2021, p.224f) (Paulich et al. 2021, p.17). The majority of the research in the field concentrates on different negative mental health outcomes (Schønning et al. 2020, p.1) including depression, anxiety, self-harm related behaviour or adverse social effects such as fear of missing out. The connections between the above mentioned adverse social media effects on mental health are acknowledged by several cross-sectional studies, but because of the cross-sectional design, the directions of those connections could not be identified (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.10). The most researched mental health outcome- depression (Schønning et al. 2020) is connected to social media usage, according to a longitudinal study (Kelly et al. 2018), but another longitudinal research fails to repeat those findings and reports no connection between overall mental health and social media (Beeres et al. 2021). Links between social media and anxiety, social media and fear of missing out, and finally social media and self-harm are reported by several cross-sectional studies (Malaeb et al. 2021) (Barthorpe et al. 2020, p.6f). Finally, the effects of social media and screen time on mental health can be severely mediated by several factors, such as cyberbullying (Viner et al. 2019, p.694f), sleep (Alonzo et al. 2021), the Covid-19 Pandemic (Haddad et al. 2021) (Valdez et al. 2020, p.4f), and physical activity (2019, p.694f). The main limitations of this paper are the scope of the study and the lack of enough longitudinal studies, that can demonstrate the direction of the social media and

screen times connection to mental health. However, this review has important implications in the research field, because it is the first one to take into account screen time effects in conjunction with social media effects on mental health and it identifies important gaps in the existing research. More longitudinal research is needed in order to investigate the direction of social media and screen time connections to mental health. Additionally, the research field would immensely benefit from clear and consistent mental health definitions, examination of one particular mental health outcome (e.g. depression) and its connection to social media or screen time and finally, future research should focus more on the mediating factors in the complex relationship between social media, screen time and mental health.

8. References

- Abi-Jaoude, E., K. T. Naylor, and A. Pignatiello. 2020. "Smartphones, social media use and youth mental health." *Cmaj* 192 (6):E136-e141. doi: 10.1503/cmaj.190434.
- Allen, Mark S., and Stewart A. Vella. 2015. "Screen-based sedentary behaviour and psychosocial well-being in childhood: Cross-sectional and longitudinal associations." *Mental Health and Physical Activity* 9:41-47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2015.10.002>.
- Alonzo, R., J. Hussain, S. Stranges, and K. K. Anderson. 2021. "Interplay between social media use, sleep quality, and mental health in youth: A systematic review." *Sleep Med Rev* 56:101414. doi: 10.1016/j.smr.2020.101414.
- Anderson, Monica and , and Jingjing Jiang. 2018. "Teens, Social Media and Technology 2018." Pew Research Center <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/05/31/teens-social-media-technology-2018/>.
- Anderson, S. E., C. D. Economos, and A. Must. 2008. "Active play and screen time in US children aged 4 to 11 years in relation to sociodemographic and weight status characteristics: a nationally representative cross-sectional analysis." *BMC Public Health* 8:366. doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-8-366.
- Babic, Mark J., Jordan J. Smith, Philip J. Morgan, Narelle Eather, Ronald C. Plotnikoff, and David R. Lubans. 2017. "Longitudinal associations between changes in screen-time and mental health outcomes in adolescents." *Mental Health and Physical Activity* 12:124-131. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2017.04.001>.
- Bailey, E., A. Boland, I. Bell, J. Nicholas, L. La Sala, and J. Robinson. 2022. "The Mental Health and Social Media Use of Young Australians during the COVID-19 Pandemic." *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 19 (3). doi: 10.3390/ijerph19031077.
- Barry, C. T., C. L. Sidoti, S. M. Briggs, S. R. Reiter, and R. A. Lindsey. 2017. "Adolescent social media use and mental health from adolescent and parent perspectives." *J Adolesc* 61:1-11. doi: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.08.005.
- Barthorpe, A., L. Winstone, B. Mars, and P. Moran. 2020. "Is social media screen time really associated with poor adolescent mental health? A time use diary study." *J Affect Disord* 274:864-870. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2020.05.106.
- Beeres, D. T., F. Andersson, H. G. M. Vossen, and M. R. Galanti. 2021. "Social Media and Mental Health Among Early Adolescents in Sweden: A Longitudinal Study

- With 2-Year Follow-Up (KUPOL Study)." *J Adolesc Health* 68 (5):953-960. doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2020.07.042.
- Bekalu, M. A., R. F. McCloud, and K. Viswanath. 2019. "Association of Social Media Use With Social Well-Being, Positive Mental Health, and Self-Rated Health: Disentangling Routine Use From Emotional Connection to Use." *Health Educ Behav* 46 (2_suppl):69-80. doi: 10.1177/1090198119863768.
- Berryman, C., C. J. Ferguson, and C. Negy. 2018. "Social Media Use and Mental Health among Young Adults." *Psychiatr Q* 89 (2):307-314. doi: 10.1007/s11126-017-9535-6.
- Beyens, Ine, Eline Frison, and Steven Eggermont. 2016. "'I don't want to miss a thing': Adolescents' fear of missing out and its relationship to adolescents' social needs, Facebook use, and Facebook related stress." *Computers in Human Behavior* 64:1-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.05.083>.
- boyd, danah m., and Nicole B. Ellison. 2007. "Social Network Sites: Definition, History, and Scholarship." *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 13 (1):210-230. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00393.x>.
- Bucksch, J., J. Inchley, Z. Hamrik, E. Finne, and P. Kolip. 2014. "Trends in television time, non-gaming PC use and moderate-to-vigorous physical activity among German adolescents 2002-2010." *BMC Public Health* 14:351. doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-14-351.
- Center, Pew Research. 2018. "Social Media Fact Sheet." Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewinternet.org/fact-sheet/social-media/>.
- Christakis, D. A., and F. J. Zimmerman. 2006. *The Elephant In The Living Room: Make Television Work for Your Kids*: Harmony/Rodale.
- da Silva, Marianne Lucena, Rodrigo Santiago Barbosa Rocha, Mohamed Buheji, Haitham Jahrami, and Katiane da Costa Cunha. 2021. "A systematic review of the prevalence of anxiety symptoms during coronavirus epidemics." *Journal of Health Psychology* 26 (1):115-125. doi: 10.1177/1359105320951620.
- de Rezende, L. F., M. Rodrigues Lopes, J. P. Rey-López, V. K. Matsudo, and C. Luiz Odo. 2014. "Sedentary behavior and health outcomes: an overview of systematic reviews." *PLoS One* 9 (8):e105620. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0105620.
- Fardouly, J., N. R. Magson, C. J. Johnco, E. L. Oar, and R. M. Rapee. 2018. "Parental Control of the Time Preadolescents Spend on Social Media: Links with

- Preadolescents' Social Media Appearance Comparisons and Mental Health." *J Youth Adolesc* 47 (7):1456-1468. doi: 10.1007/s10964-018-0870-1.
- Fardouly, J., N. R. Magson, R. M. Rapee, C. J. Johnco, and E. L. Oar. 2020. "The use of social media by Australian preadolescents and its links with mental health." *J Clin Psychol* 76 (7):1304-1326. doi: 10.1002/jclp.22936.
- Flynn, H. C., S. L. Mote, and B. L. Morse. 2022. "Social Media and Adolescent Mental Health: Sounding the Alarm." *NASN Sch Nurse*:1942602x221079758. doi: 10.1177/1942602x221079758.
- Galderisi, S., A. Heinz, M. Kastrup, J. Beezhold, and N. Sartorius. 2015. "Toward a new definition of mental health." *World Psychiatry* 14 (2):231-3. doi: 10.1002/wps.20231.
- Gramlich, John. 2021. "10 facts about Americans and Facebook." <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/06/01/facts-about-americans-and-facebook/>.
- Gunnell, Katie E., Martine F. Flament, Annick Buchholz, Katherine A. Henderson, Nicole Obeid, Nicholas Schubert, and Gary S. Goldfield. 2016. "Examining the bidirectional relationship between physical activity, screen time, and symptoms of anxiety and depression over time during adolescence." *Preventive Medicine* 88:147-152. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2016.04.002>.
- Haddad, J. M., C. Macenski, A. Mosier-Mills, A. Hibara, K. Kester, M. Schneider, R. C. Conrad, and C. H. Liu. 2021. "The Impact of Social Media on College Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: a Multinational Review of the Existing Literature." *Curr Psychiatry Rep* 23 (11):70. doi: 10.1007/s11920-021-01288-y.
- Hinduja, Sameer, and Justin W. Patchin. 2008. "Cyberbullying: An Exploratory Analysis of Factors Related to Offending and Victimization." *Deviant Behavior* 29 (2):129-156. doi: 10.1080/01639620701457816.
- Hinkley, Trina, Vera Verbestel, Wolfgang Ahrens, Lauren Lissner, Dénes Molnár, Luis A. Moreno, Iris Pigeot, Hermann Pohlmann, Lucia A. Reisch, Paola Russo, Toomas Veidebaum, Michael Tornaritis, Garrath Williams, Stefaan De Henauw, Ilse De Bourdeaudhuij, and Idefics Consortium for the. 2014. "Early Childhood Electronic Media Use as a Predictor of Poorer Well-being: A Prospective Cohort Study." *JAMA Pediatrics* 168 (5):485-492. doi: 10.1001/jamapediatrics.2014.94.
- Hong, Soon-Beom, Jae-Won Kim, Eun-Jung Choi, Ho-Hyun Kim, Jeong-Eun Suh, Chang-Dai Kim, Paul Klauser, Sarah Whittle, Murat Yücel, Christos Pantelis, and

- Soon-Hyung Yi. 2013. "Reduced orbitofrontal cortical thickness in male adolescents with internet addiction." *Behavioral and Brain Functions* 9 (1):11. doi: 10.1186/1744-9081-9-11.
- Hrafnkeldsottir, S. M., R. J. Brychta, V. Rognvaldsdottir, S. Gestsdottir, K. Y. Chen, E. Johannsson, S. L. Guðmundsdottir, and S. A. Arngrimsson. 2018. "Less screen time and more frequent vigorous physical activity is associated with lower risk of reporting negative mental health symptoms among Icelandic adolescents." *PLoS One* 13 (4):e0196286. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0196286.
- Huang, C. 2022. "A meta-analysis of the problematic social media use and mental health." *Int J Soc Psychiatry* 68 (1):12-33. doi: 10.1177/0020764020978434.
- Ifinedo, Princely. 2016. "Applying uses and gratifications theory and social influence processes to understand students' pervasive adoption of social networking sites: Perspectives from the Americas." *International Journal of Information Management* 36 (2):192-206. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2015.11.007>.
- John, A., A. C. Glendenning, A. Marchant, P. Montgomery, A. Stewart, S. Wood, K. Lloyd, and K. Hawton. 2018. "Self-Harm, Suicidal Behaviours, and Cyberbullying in Children and Young People: Systematic Review." *J Med Internet Res* 20 (4):e129. doi: 10.2196/jmir.9044.
- Karim, F., A. A. Oyewande, L. F. Abdalla, R. Chaudhry Ehsanullah, and S. Khan. 2020. "Social Media Use and Its Connection to Mental Health: A Systematic Review." *Cureus* 12 (6):e8627. doi: 10.7759/cureus.8627.
- Keles, Betül, Niall McCrae, and Annmarie Grealish. 2020. "A systematic review: the influence of social media on depression, anxiety and psychological distress in adolescents." *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth* 25 (1):79-93. doi: 10.1080/02673843.2019.1590851.
- Kelly, Y., A. Zilanawala, C. Booker, and A. Sacker. 2018. "Social Media Use and Adolescent Mental Health: Findings From the UK Millennium Cohort Study." *EClinicalMedicine* 6:59-68. doi: 10.1016/j.eclinm.2018.12.005.
- Kieling, Christian, Helen Baker-Henningham, Myron Belfer, Gabriella Conti, Ilgi Ertem, Olayinka Omigbodun, Luis Augusto Rohde, Shoba Srinath, Nurper Ulkuer, and Atif Rahman. 2011. "Child and adolescent mental health worldwide: evidence for action." *The Lancet* 378 (9801):1515-1525. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)60827-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60827-1).

- Kietzmann, Jan H., Kristopher Hermkens, Ian P. McCarthy, and Bruno S. Silvestre. 2011. "Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media." *Business Horizons* 54 (3):241-251. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.005>.
- Kim, Soyeon, Melissa Kimber, Michael H. Boyle, and Katholiki Georgiades. 2018. "Sex Differences in the Association Between Cyberbullying Victimization and Mental Health, Substance Use, and Suicidal Ideation in Adolescents." *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry* 64 (2):126-135. doi: 10.1177/0706743718777397.
- Kross, Ethan, Philippe Verduyn, Emre Demiralp, Jiyoung Park, David Seungjae Lee, Natalie Lin, Holly Shablack, John Jonides, and Oscar Ybarra. 2013. "Facebook Use Predicts Declines in Subjective Well-Being in Young Adults." *PLOS ONE* 8 (8):e69841. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0069841.
- Latha, K., K. S. Meena, M. R. Pravitha, M. Dasgupta, and S. K. Chaturvedi. 2020. "Effective use of social media platforms for promotion of mental health awareness." *J Educ Health Promot* 9:124. doi: 10.4103/jehp.jehp_90_20.
- Lin, C. Y., P. Namdar, M. D. Griffiths, and A. H. Pakpour. 2021. "Mediated roles of generalized trust and perceived social support in the effects of problematic social media use on mental health: A cross-sectional study." *Health Expect* 24 (1):165-173. doi: 10.1111/hex.13169.
- Linebarger, Deborah L., and Dale Walker. 2005. "Infants' and Toddlers' Television Viewing and Language Outcomes." *American Behavioral Scientist* 48 (5):624-645. doi: 10.1177/0002764204271505.
- Lu, Y., T. Pan, J. Liu, and J. Wu. 2020. "Does Usage of Online Social Media Help Users With Depressed Symptoms Improve Their Mental Health? Empirical Evidence From an Online Depression Community." *Front Public Health* 8:581088. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2020.581088.
- Madigan, Sheri, Dillon Browne, Nicole Racine, Camille Mori, and Suzanne Tough. 2019. "Association Between Screen Time and Children's Performance on a Developmental Screening Test." *JAMA Pediatrics* 173 (3):244-250. doi: 10.1001/jamapediatrics.2018.5056.
- Malaeb, D., P. Salameh, S. Barbar, E. Awad, C. Haddad, R. Hallit, H. Sacre, M. Akel, S. Obeid, and S. Hallit. 2021. "Problematic social media use and mental health (depression, anxiety, and insomnia) among Lebanese adults: Any mediating effect of stress?" *Perspect Psychiatr Care* 57 (2):539-549. doi: 10.1111/ppc.12576.

- Maras, Danijela, Martine F. Flament, Marisa Murray, Annick Buchholz, Katherine A. Henderson, Nicole Obeid, and Gary S. Goldfield. 2015. "Screen time is associated with depression and anxiety in Canadian youth." *Preventive Medicine* 73:133-138. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2015.01.029>.
- Mehmet, Michael, Russell Roberts, and Tahmid Nayeem. 2020. "Using digital and social media for health promotion: A social marketing approach for addressing co-morbid physical and mental health." *Australian Journal of Rural Health* 28 (2):149-158. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajr.12589>.
- Muniswamy, P., V. Gorhe, L. Parashivakumar, and B. Chandrasekaran. 2021. "Short-term effects of a social media-based intervention on the physical and mental health of remotely working young software professionals: A randomised controlled trial." *Appl Psychol Health Well Being*. doi: 10.1111/aphw.12318.
- Nadkarni, A., and S. G. Hofmann. 2012. "Why Do People Use Facebook?" *Pers Individ Dif* 52 (3):243-249. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2011.11.007.
- Neophytou, Eliana, Laurie A. Manwell, and Roelof Eikelboom. 2021. "Effects of Excessive Screen Time on Neurodevelopment, Learning, Memory, Mental Health, and Neurodegeneration: a Scoping Review." *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction* 19 (3):724-744. doi: 10.1007/s11469-019-00182-2.
- Nesi, J. 2020. "The Impact of Social Media on Youth Mental Health: Challenges and Opportunities." *N C Med J* 81 (2):116-121. doi: 10.18043/ncm.81.2.116.
- Neubaum, German, and Nicole C. Krämer. 2015. "My Friends Right Next to Me: A Laboratory Investigation on Predictors and Consequences of Experiencing Social Closeness on Social Networking Sites." *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking* 18 (8):443-449. doi: 10.1089/cyber.2014.0613.
- Nigg, C. R., K. Wunsch, C. Nigg, C. Niessner, D. Jekauc, S. C. E. Schmidt, and A. Woll. 2021. "Are Physical Activity, Screen Time, and Mental Health Related During Childhood, Preadolescence, and Adolescence? 11-Year Results From the German Motorik-Modul Longitudinal Study." *Am J Epidemiol* 190 (2):220-229. doi: 10.1093/aje/kwaa192.
- O'Reilly, M. 2020. "Social media and adolescent mental health: the good, the bad and the ugly." *J Ment Health* 29 (2):200-206. doi: 10.1080/09638237.2020.1714007.
- O'Reilly, M., N. Dogra, J. Hughes, P. Reilly, R. George, and N. Whiteman. 2019. "Potential of social media in promoting mental health in adolescents." *Health Promot Int* 34 (5):981-991. doi: 10.1093/heapro/day056.

- Paulich, K. N., J. M. Ross, J. M. Lessem, and J. K. Hewitt. 2021. "Screen time and early adolescent mental health, academic, and social outcomes in 9- and 10- year old children: Utilizing the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development SM (ABCD) Study." *PLoS One* 16 (9):e0256591. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0256591.
- Petrosino, Anthony, Robert F. Boruch, Haluk Soydan, Lorna Duggan, and Julio Sanchez-Meca. 2001. "Meeting the Challenges of Evidence-Based Policy: The Campbell Collaboration." *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 578 (1):14-34. doi: 10.1177/000271620157800102.
- Pfefferbaum, Betty, and Carol S. North. 2020. "Mental Health and the Covid-19 Pandemic." *New England Journal of Medicine* 383 (6):510-512. doi: 10.1056/NEJMp2008017.
- Pittman, Matthew, and Emil Steiner. 2021. "Distinguishing feast-watching from cringe-watching: Planned, social, and attentive binge-watching predicts increased well-being and decreased regret." *Convergence* 27 (5):1507-1524. doi: 10.1177/1354856521999183.
- Raza, S. H., M. Yousaf, F. Sohail, R. Munawar, E. C. Ogadimma, and Jmld Siang. 2021. "Investigating Binge-Watching Adverse Mental Health Outcomes During Covid-19 Pandemic: Moderating Role of Screen Time for Web Series Using Online Streaming." *Psychol Res Behav Manag* 14:1615-1629. doi: 10.2147/prbm.S328416.
- Sarangi, A., W. Amor, E. L. F. Co, S. Javed, S. Usmani, and A. Rashid. 2022. "Social Media Reinvented: Can Social Media Help Tackle the Post-Pandemic Mental Health Onslaught?" *Cureus* 14 (1):e21070. doi: 10.7759/cureus.21070.
- Schmiedeberg, Claudia, and Jette Schröder. 2017. "Leisure Activities and Life Satisfaction: an Analysis with German Panel Data." *Applied Research in Quality of Life* 12 (1):137-151. doi: 10.1007/s11482-016-9458-7.
- Schønning, V., G. J. Hjetland, L. E. Aarø, and J. C. Skogen. 2020. "Social Media Use and Mental Health and Well-Being Among Adolescents - A Scoping Review." *Front Psychol* 11:1949. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01949.
- Seabrook, E. M., M. L. Kern, and N. S. Rickard. 2016. "Social Networking Sites, Depression, and Anxiety: A Systematic Review." *JMIR Ment Health* 3 (4):e50. doi: 10.2196/mental.5842.

- Sharma, M. K., N. John, and M. Sahu. 2020. "Influence of social media on mental health: a systematic review." *Curr Opin Psychiatry* 33 (5):467-475. doi: 10.1097/ycp.0000000000000631.
- Silver, Laura. 2019. "Smartphone Ownership Is Growing Rapidly Around the World, but Not Always Equally." Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/2019/02/05/smartphone-ownership-is-growing-rapidly-around-the-world-but-not-always-equally/>.
- Skogen, J. C., G. J. Hjetland, T. Bøe, R. T. Hella, and A. K. Knudsen. 2021. "Through the Looking Glass of Social Media. Focus on Self-Presentation and Association with Mental Health and Quality of Life. A Cross-Sectional Survey-Based Study." *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 18 (6). doi: 10.3390/ijerph18063319.
- Smith, L., L. Jacob, M. Trott, A. Yakkundi, L. Butler, Y. Barnett, N. C. Armstrong, D. McDermott, F. Schuch, J. Meyer, R. López-Bueno, G. F. L. Sánchez, D. Bradley, and M. A. Tully. 2020. "The association between screen time and mental health during COVID-19: A cross sectional study." *Psychiatry Res* 292:113333. doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113333.
- Srivastava, K., S. Chaudhury, J. Prakash, and S. Dhamija. 2019. "Social media and mental health challenges." *Ind Psychiatry J* 28 (2):155-159. doi: 10.4103/ipj.ipj_154_20.
- Starosta, Jolanta A., and Bernadetta Izydorczyk. 2020. "Understanding the Phenomenon of Binge-Watching—A Systematic Review." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17 (12):4469.
- Statista. 2020. "Share of individuals who used online social networks every day or almost every day in the European Union (EU 28) from 2011 to 2019." European Commission <https://www.statista.com/statistics/452434/europe-daily-online-social-network-usage/>.
- Statista. 2022. "Number of social network users worldwide from 2017 to 2025 (in billions)." Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/278414/number-of-worldwide-social-network-users/#statisticContainer>.
- Sujarwoto, R. A. M. Saputri, and T. Yumarni. 2021. "Social Media Addiction and Mental Health Among University Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia." *Int J Ment Health Addict*:1-15. doi: 10.1007/s11469-021-00582-3.
- Tang, S., A. Werner-Seidler, M. Torok, A. J. Mackinnon, and H. Christensen. 2021. "The relationship between screen time and mental health in young people: A systematic

- review of longitudinal studies." *Clin Psychol Rev* 86:102021. doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2021.102021.
- Toma, C. L., and J. T. Hancock. 2013. "Self-affirmation underlies Facebook use." *Pers Soc Psychol Bull* 39 (3):321-31. doi: 10.1177/0146167212474694.
- Tromholt, Morten. 2016. "The Facebook Experiment: Quitting Facebook Leads to Higher Levels of Well-Being." *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking* 19 (11):661-666. doi: 10.1089/cyber.2016.0259.
- Twenge, J. M., and E. Farley. 2021. "Not all screen time is created equal: associations with mental health vary by activity and gender." *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol* 56 (2):207-217. doi: 10.1007/s00127-020-01906-9.
- Twenge, J. M., J. Haidt, J. Lozano, and K. M. Cummins. 2022. "Specification curve analysis shows that social media use is linked to poor mental health, especially among girls." *Acta Psychol (Amst)* 224:103512. doi: 10.1016/j.actpsy.2022.103512.
- Twenge, Jean M., and W. Keith Campbell. 2018. "Associations between screen time and lower psychological well-being among children and adolescents: Evidence from a population-based study." *Preventive Medicine Reports* 12:271-283. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2018.10.003>.
- Twenge, Jean, Gabrielle Martin, and Brian Spitzberg. 2018. "Trends in U.S. Adolescents' Media Use, 1976-2016: The Rise of Digital Media, the Decline of TV, and the (Near) Demise of Print." *Psychology of Popular Media Culture* 8. doi: 10.1037/ppm0000203.
- Valdez, D., M. Ten Thij, K. Bathina, L. A. Rutter, and J. Bollen. 2020. "Social Media Insights Into US Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Longitudinal Analysis of Twitter Data." *J Med Internet Res* 22 (12):e21418. doi: 10.2196/21418.
- Valkenburg, P. M., A. Meier, and I. Beyens. 2021. "Social media use and its impact on adolescent mental health: An umbrella review of the evidence." *Curr Opin Psychol* 44:58-68. doi: 10.1016/j.copsyc.2021.08.017.
- Viner, R. M., A. Gireesh, N. Stiglic, L. D. Hudson, A. L. Goddings, J. L. Ward, and D. E. Nicholls. 2019. "Roles of cyberbullying, sleep, and physical activity in mediating the effects of social media use on mental health and wellbeing among young people in England: a secondary analysis of longitudinal data." *Lancet Child Adolesc Health* 3 (10):685-696. doi: 10.1016/s2352-4642(19)30186-5.

- Vogel, Erin A., Jason P. Rose, Bradley M. Okdie, Katheryn Eckles, and Brittany Franz. 2015. "Who compares and despairs? The effect of social comparison orientation on social media use and its outcomes." *Personality and Individual Differences* 86:249-256. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.06.026>.
- WHO. 2019. "Mental health: Fact sheet." World Health Organisation. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/404851/MNH_FactSheet_ENG.pdf.
- WHO. 2022. "Mental health." https://www.who.int/health-topics/mental-health#tab=tab_2.
- Wolke, Dieter, Kirsty Lee, and Alexa Guy. 2017. "Cyberbullying: a storm in a teacup?" *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 26 (8):899-908. doi: 10.1007/s00787-017-0954-6.
- Woo, K. S., S. H. Bong, T. Y. Choi, and J. W. Kim. 2021. "Mental Health, Smartphone Use Type, and Screen Time Among Adolescents in South Korea." *Psychol Res Behav Manag* 14:1419-1428. doi: 10.2147/prbm.S324235.
- Young, L., D. C. Kolubinski, and D. Frings. 2020. "Attachment style moderates the relationship between social media use and user mental health and wellbeing." *Heliyon* 6 (6):e04056. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04056.
- Zhao, Xuan, Cliff Lampe, and Nicole Ellison. 2016. *The Social Media Ecology: User Perceptions, Strategies and Challenges*.
- Zhong, B., Z. Jiang, W. Xie, and X. Qin. 2020. "Association of Social Media Use With Mental Health Conditions of Nonpatients During the COVID-19 Outbreak: Insights from a National Survey Study." *J Med Internet Res* 22 (12):e23696. doi: 10.2196/23696.
- Zimmerman, Frederick J., Dimitri A. Christakis, and Andrew N. Meltzoff. 2007. "Television and DVD/Video Viewing in Children Younger Than 2 Years." *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine* 161 (5):473-479. doi: 10.1001/archpedi.161.5.473.

Appendix

Table 3

Author	Title	Method	Findings
C. T. Barry, C. L. Sidoti, S. M. Briggs, S. R. Reiter and R. A. Lindsey	Adolescent social media use and mental health from adolescent and parent perspectives	Quantitative Study	The reports of the number of adolescents' social media accounts were moderately correlated with parent-reported symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity/impulsivity, ODD, anxiety, and depressive symptoms, as well as adolescent-reported fear of missing out (FoMO) and loneliness. Lastly, anxiety and depressive symptoms were highest among adolescents with a relatively high number of parent-reported social media accounts and relatively high FoMO.
C. Berryman, C. J. Ferguson and C. Negy	Social Media Use and Mental Health among Young Adults	Quantitative Study	Results indicated that social media use was not predictive of impaired mental health functioning. However, vaguebooking was predictive of suicidal ideation, suggesting this particular behaviour could be a warning sign for serious issues.
J. Fardouly, N. R. Magson, C. J. Johnco, E. L. Oar and R. M. Rapee	Parental Control of the Time Preadolescents Spend on Social Media: Links with Preadolescents' Social Media Appearance Comparisons and Mental Health	Quantitative Study	Greater parental control over how much time preadolescent children spend on social media was linked to greater preadolescent mental health (depressive symptoms, appearance satisfaction, life satisfaction). Mediators are less preadolescent time spent exploring social media and less preadolescent appearance comparison frequency on social media.
S. M. Hrafnkelsdottir, R. J. Brychta, V.	Less screen time and more frequent vigorous physical	Cross-Sectional	Less screen time and more frequent intense physical exercise were both associated

Rognvaldsdottir, S. Gestsdottir, K. Y. Chen, E. Johannsson, et al.	activity is associated with lower risk of reporting negative mental health symptoms among Icelandic adolescents		with a lower likelihood of reporting symptoms of depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, and life dissatisfaction. Those who reported reduced screen time in combination with more frequent vigorous physical exercise had the lowest likelihood of reporting poor mental health symptoms
Y. Kelly, A. Zilanawala, C. Booker and A. Sacker	Social Media Use and Adolescent Mental Health: Findings From the UK Millennium Cohort Study	Longitudinal	Girls had a stronger connection between social media use and depressive symptoms than boys. Increased social media use was associated with online harassment, poor sleep, low self-esteem, and poor body image, all of which were associated with greater depressed symptom ratings.
M. A. Bekalu, R. F. McCloud and K. Viswanath	Association of Social Media Use With Social Well-Being, Positive Mental Health, and Self-Rated Health: Disentangling Routine Use From Emotional Connection to Use	Cross-Sectional	While routine use was linked to positive health outcomes, the emotional attachment was linked to negative results, a finding that was similar throughout the three health-related outcomes of interest: social well-being, positive mental health, and self-rated health.
M. O'Reilly, N. Dogra, J. Hughes, P. Reilly, R. George and N. Whiteman	Potential of social media in promoting mental health in adolescents	Qualitative study	It appears that social media has the ability to enhance positive mental health. Teens commonly use social media and the internet to research mental health issues. Finally, there are advantages and disadvantages to using social media in this manner.
K. Srivastava, S. Chaudhury, J. Prakash and S. Dhamija	Social media and mental health challenges	Review Article	When utilized responsibly, social media may provide enormous benefits. Social media is omnipresent and has permeated a wide range of activities, including government, business, commerce, education, and information technology. The negative effects of social media

			may have serious ramifications for young people.
R. M. Viner, A. Gireesh, N. Stiglic, L. D. Hudson, A. L. Goddings, J. L. Ward, et al.	Roles of cyberbullying, sleep, and physical activity in mediating the effects of social media use on mental health and wellbeing among young people in England: a secondary analysis of longitudinal data	Longitudinal	The study discovered significant, longitudinal correlations between highly frequent social media usage and mental health and wellbeing in girls, which were predominantly mediated by cyberbullying and sleep and physical activity. The same characteristics mediated this link in boys, although to a much lesser extent; the study shows that much of the harm associated with social media is likely to be attributable to the content consumed (e.g., cyberbullying) or the displacement of healthy quantities of sleep and physical exercise.
E. Abi-Jaoude, K. T. Naylor and A. Pignatiello	Smartphones, social media use and youth mental health	Review Article	There is a dose-response association between smartphone and social media use and an increase in mental distress, self-injurious behaviour, and suicidality among youth; the effects appear to be greatest among girls. Social media can have an impact on teenagers' self-esteem and interpersonal connections through social comparison and unpleasant interactions, such as cyberbullying; also, social media content frequently normalizes and even promotes self-harm and suicidality among youth. Youth participate in high levels of smartphone use and media multitasking, resulting in chronic sleep deprivation and poor impacts on cognitive control, academic performance, and emotional functioning in the society.

A. Barthorpe, L. Winstone, B. Mars and P. Moran	Is social media screen time really associated with poor adolescent mental health? A time use diary study	Cross-Sectional	In females, more time spent on social media was connected with an increased risk of self-harm and depression, as well as poorer levels of self-esteem. After controlling for confounders such as prior mental health problems, the findings were consistent.
J. Fardouly, N. R. Magson, R. M. Rapee, C. J. Johnco and E. L. Oar	The use of social media by Australian preadolescents and its links with mental health	Cross-Sectional	More time spent on all three platforms was associated with lower body satisfaction, while more time spent on YouTube was connected with increased depression symptoms. These associations, however, were minor.
F. Karim, A. A. Oyewande, L. F. Abdalla, R. Chaudhry Ehsanullah and S. Khan	Social Media Use and Its Connection to Mental Health: A Systematic Review	Systematic Review	This systematic review has found that social media envy can affect the level of anxiety and depression in individuals.
K. Latha, K. S. Meena, M. R. Pravitha, M. Dasgupta and S. K. Chaturvedi	Effective use of social media platforms for promotion of mental health awareness	Qualitative study	The use of social media to conduct mental health campaigns is an effective initiative as one can reach out to several people over a short time period.
Y. Lu, T. Pan, J. Liu and J. Wu	Does Usage of Online Social Media Help Users With Depressed Symptoms Improve Their Mental Health? Empirical Evidence From an Online Depression Community	Longitudinal	The findings show that a sense of shared identity, trust, informational support, and emotional support are all beneficial to depression, however, socializing support is detrimental. Female users experience more good impacts from a sense of shared identity and trust than male users, and male users experience more negative consequences from socializing support.
J. Nesi	The Impact of Social Media on Youth Mental Health: Challenges and Opportunities	Review Article/ Commentary	Cyberbullying, social exclusion, sleep disruptions; potential benefits including creative expression, social connectedness and machine learning that detects mental illness.

M. O'Reilly	Social media and adolescent mental health: the good, the bad and the ugly	Qualitative study	Much of the negative rhetoric of social media was repeated by mental health practitioners, although there was some acknowledgement of potential benefits.
V. Schönning, G. J. Hjetland, L. E. Aarø and J. C. Skogen	Social Media Use and Mental Health and Well-Being Among Adolescents - A Scoping Review	Scoping Review	According to the results of the current scoping review, nearly 3/4 of the included research focused on social media and pathology in some way. In the current studies, there appears to be less emphasis on the potential link between social media use and positive outcomes.
M. K. Sharma, N. John and M. Sahu	Influence of social media on mental health: a systematic review	Systematic Review	Although there are advantages to using social media, one cannot overlook how technological improvements have extended access to social media while also increasing the number of negative impacts. The debate over social media's impact on mental health will continue until more randomized controlled trials are completed.
L. Smith, L. Jacob, M. Trott, A. Yakkundi, L. Butler, Y. Barnett, et al.	The association between screen time and mental health during COVID-19: A cross-sectional study	Cross-Sectional	In the entire sample, there was a link between screen use per day in hours and poor mental health. The link between daily screen usage and poor mental health was also discovered to be significant in women and adults aged 35–64 years, regardless of gender.
D. Valdez, M. Ten Thij, K. Bathina, L. A. Rutter and J. Bollen	Social Media Insights Into US Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Longitudinal Analysis of Twitter Data	Longitudinal	Higher use rates show that social media may be a coping mechanism for certain people dealing with emotions of loneliness brought on by long-term social isolation. However, given the established harmful effects of extensive social media use on mental health, many people's unpleasant moods may be exacerbated by social media in the long run.

L. Young, D. C. Kolubinski and D. Frings	Attachment style moderates the relationship between social media use and user mental health and wellbeing	Cross-Sectional	People who are strong in anxious attachment and low in attachment avoidance are more likely to report much greater levels of depressed symptoms from problematic social media use.
B. Zhong, Z. Jiang, W. Xie and X. Qin	Association of Social Media Use With Mental Health Conditions of Nonpatients During the COVID-19 Outbreak: Insights from a National Survey Study	Quantitative Study	During the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a link between social media use and psychiatric problems in the general public; the causation of such psychiatric disorders are complicated and diverse, and social media use is a potential contributor.
R. Alonzo, J. Hussain, S. Stranges and K. K. Anderson	Interplay between social media use, sleep quality, and mental health in youth: A systematic review	Systematic Review	Excessive social media use is linked to poor sleep quality and low mental health in youth, according to the data. Given the public health significance of sleep issues, further research is needed to determine the directionality and degree of social media's links to poor sleep quality and bad mental health consequences.
D. T. Beeres, F. Andersson, H. G. M. Vossen and M. R. Galanti	Social Media and Mental Health Among Early Adolescents in Sweden: A Longitudinal Study With 2-Year Follow-Up (KUPOL Study)	Longitudinal	Adolescents who use social media more frequently report more symptoms of mental illness, but there is no evidence of a long-term link between increased use and mental illness. This shows that social media is more of an indicator than a risk factor for mental illness symptoms.
J. M. Haddad, C. Macenski, A. Mosier-Mills, A. Hibara, K. Kester, M. Schneider, et al.	The Impact of Social Media on College Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: a Multinational Review of the Existing Literature	Review Article	During the COVID-19 pandemic, excessive or problematic social media use was linked to poorer mental health outcomes, which may be alleviated by dialectical thinking, positivity, mindfulness, and cognitive reappraisal. By strengthening the link between social media use and mental health, the

			COVID-19 epidemic functions as a moderator.
C. Y. Lin, P. Namdar, M. D. Griffiths and A. H. Pakpour	Mediated roles of generalized trust and perceived social support in the effects of problematic social media use on mental health: A cross-sectional study	Cross-Sectional	Through the mediators of generalized trust, problematic social media use had a negative impact on happiness and mental quality of life and a beneficial influence on anxiety and depression.
D. Malaeb, P. Salameh, S. Barbar, E. Awad, C. Haddad, R. Hallit, et al.	Problematic social media use and mental health (depression, anxiety, and insomnia) among Lebanese adults: Any mediating effect of stress?	Cross-Sectional	Increased levels of problematic social media use were linked to higher levels of depression, anxiety, and insomnia, but not stress. The link between depression, anxiety, insomnia, and problematic social media use was mediated by stress.
P. Muniswamy, V. Gorhe, L. Parashivakumar and B. Chandrasekaran	Short-term effects of social media-based intervention on the physical and mental health of remotely working young software professionals: A randomised controlled trial	Randomised Controlled Trial	Quick social media-based physical and mental health interventions could help office workers working remotely boost their physical and mental health.
C. R. Nigg, K. Wunsch, C. Nigg, C. Niessner, D. Jekauc, S. C. E. Schmidt, et al.	Are Physical Activity, Screen Time, and Mental Health Related During Childhood, Preadolescence, and Adolescence? 11-Year Results From the German Motorik-Modul Longitudinal Study	Longitudinal	Females' self-reported mental health in preadolescence and adolescence appears to be negatively impacted by screen time in childhood and preadolescence, whereas males' self-reported mental health in preadolescence appears to be a potential risk for adolescent screen time.
K. N. Paulich, J. M. Ross, J. M. Lessem and J. K. Hewitt	Screen time and early adolescent mental health, academic, and social outcomes in 9- and 10- year old children: Utilizing	Longitudinal	Total screen time usage on weekdays and weekends is moderately linked to increased behavioural issues such as ADHD, poor academic performance, and poor sleep quantity and quality and screen

	the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development SM (ABCD) Study		time are linked to the quantity and quality of peer connections, both irrespective of gender.
S. H. Raza, M. Yousaf, F. Sohail, R. Munawar, E. C. Ogadimma and J. Siang	Investigating Binge-Watching Adverse Mental Health Outcomes During Covid-19 Pandemic: Moderating Role of Screen Time for Web Series Using Online Streaming	Cross-Sectional	Stress, loneliness, insomnia, depression, and anxiety are all linked to binge-watching. Furthermore, screen time spent binge-watching could increase these negative impacts.
J. C. Skogen, G. J. Hjetland, T. Bøe, R. T. Hella and A. K. Knudsen	Through the Looking Glass of Social Media. Focus on Self-Presentation and Association with Mental Health and Quality of Life. A Cross-Sectional Survey-Based Study	Cross-Sectional	Focus on self-presentation has a moderately strong and persistent connection with anxiety and depression symptoms and quality of life in teenagers, with gender differences possible.
Sujarwoto, R. A. M. Saputri and T. Yumarni	Social Media Addiction and Mental Health Among University Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia	Cross-Sectional	Increased social media usage is possible to affect university students' mental health in Indonesia, as students with higher social media addiction values were at higher risk of moderate depression.
S. Tang, A. Werner-Seidler, M. Torok, A. J. Mackinnon and H. Christensen	The relationship between screen time and mental health in young people: A systematic review of longitudinal studies	Systematic Review of Longitudinal Studies	The status of the relationship between screen time and following mental health symptoms was most apparent for depression. The association between screen time and subsequent depression was stronger than the reverse relationship. Newer types of technology, such as smartphones and computers/internet showed stronger connections than older technologies, such as television and videogames.

J. M. Twenge and E. Farley	Not all screen time is created equal: associations with mental health vary by activity and gender	Cross-Sectional	Hours spent on social media and the Internet were found to be more significantly linked to self-harm, depressive symptoms, low life satisfaction, and low self-esteem than hours spent on electronic games or watching television. Girls had stronger relationships between screen media use and mental health markers than boys.
P. M. Valkenburg, A. Meier and I. Beyens	Social media use and its impact on adolescent mental health: An umbrella review of the evidence	Umbrella Review	The majority of studies labeled the links between social media use and mental health as 'weak' or 'inconsistent,' while a others called them 'substantial' and 'deleterious.' To begin, future research must clearly specify the variables and outcomes being studied.
K. S. Woo, S. H. Bong, T. Y. Choi and J. W. Kim	Mental Health, Smartphone Use Type, and Screen Time Among Adolescents in South Korea	Cross-Sectional	In both groups that used smartphones for 4 hours per day on weekdays, stress perception, sleep satisfaction, depressive symptoms, and suicide-related markers deteriorated. Using smartphones for 2 hours but less than 4 hours per day on weekends decreased sleep satisfaction and suicide-related markers in both groups. Participants' mental health increased when they used cellphones for 2 hours but less than 4 hours per day, but declined when they used smartphones for more than 4 hours per day on weekends.
E. Bailey, A. Boland, I. Bell, J. Nicholas, L. La Sala and J. Robinson	The Mental Health and Social Media Use of Young Australians during the COVID-19 Pandemic	Cross-Sectional	As a result of the epidemic, young people spend more time on social media, with high levels of daily social media use linked to poor mental health. Furthermore, young people use social media to seek and provide assistance for suicidal thoughts and self-harm, as well as to support others; taken

			together, this shows that social media may offer a way to help young people who are experiencing psychological distress and are at risk of suicide.
H. C. Flynn, S. L. Mote and B. L. Morse	Social Media and Adolescent Mental Health: Sounding the Alarm	Review Article	Despite all the good impacts on communication and sharing, studies have found that social media poses a threat to the mental health of adolescents, who are at a higher risk for mental illness due to their emotional and developmental sensitivity.
C. Huang	A meta-analysis of the problematic social media use and mental health	Meta Analysis	The average associations between problematic social media use and wellbeing are negative, while the average associations between problematic social media use and distress are positive. Problematic social media use had weak average associations with life satisfaction and self-esteem, but substantial average associations with depression and loneliness.
A. Sarangi, W. Amor, E. L. F. Co, S. Javed, S. Usmani and A. Rashid	Social Media Reinvented: Can Social Media Help Tackle the Post-Pandemic Mental Health Onslaught?	Review Article	There are ways to make beneficial use of social media's influence. This includes, but is not limited to, linking people to mental health resources, disseminating information on COVID-19 treatment options, and facilitating global social connections.
J. M. Twenge, J. Haidt, J. Lozano and K. M. Cummins	Specification curve analysis shows that social media use is linked to poor mental health, especially among girls	Specification curve analysis	There is a persistent and significant link between mental health and social media use among girls.